

NFDI4Objects

Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

KLASSIK
STIFTUNG
WEIMAR

Harmonisierung und Integration von Konsortialdiensten durch Verknüpfung dezentraler Systeme in NFDI4Objects

NFDI4Objects Community Meeting 2024 | Mainz | 25.09.2024
Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie (LEIZA) | 25. - 27. September 2024
Session: Workshop VI

Florian Thiery - Anja Gerber - Fabian Fricke

via [trentu.ca](https://www.trentu.ca)

Roland Soré, via flickr [rolibin/30105173063/](https://www.flickr.com/photos/rolibin/30105173063/)

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

archaeological_site	megalith
historic	archaeological_site
historic:civilization	neolithic
name	Crvena stijena
name:en	Red wall
wikidata	Q121418883
wikipedia	https://bs.wikipedia.org/wiki/Crvena_stijena_(Crna_Gora)

via researchgate [320957331](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320957331) The Paleolithic Faunal Remains from Crvena Stijena

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Xalaros, Attribution, via Wikimedia Commons

Forschungsdaten im Kontext von N40 sind sehr heterogen und immer im domänenbezogenen Kontext und interdisziplinär zu betrachten

**Um diese Daten untereinander austauschbar,
interoperabel und kompatibel zu machen,
sind ein gemeinsames Verständnis und eine
technische Implementierung nötig**

**Nur so kann eine übergreifende Abfrage
des resultierenden interdisziplinären
Knowledge Graphen erfolgen**

FINDABLE

ACCESSIBLE

INTEROPERABLE

REUSABLE

Dr. Heidi Seibold, CC BY 4.0, via 10.5281/zenodo.8070860

FAIRifizierung ist die Grundlage von Open Data!

via <https://5stardata.info/> and <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>

FAIR Graphen erzeugt man mit Linked Open Data

image via ontotext.com

**Linked Data basiert auf dem
Resource Description Framework (RDF)**

Florian Thiery / LEIZA, [CC BY 4.0](#), via [Wikimedia Commons](#)

Florian Thiery, [CC BY 4.0](#), via [Wikimedia Commons](#)

**Das Konzept hinter RDF sind Triples.
Die LOD Prinzipien verknüpfen RDF Daten zu ...**

Florian Thiery / LEIZA, based on lod-cloud.net, CC BY 4.0

... zu einem wachsenden LOD Knowledge Graph

NFDI4Objects

Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

FAIRifizierung ist ein Ziel von NFDI4Objects

Vanessa Liebler / NFDI4Objects, CC BY-SA 4.0

FAIRifizierung kann nur in Zusammenarbeit mit den Konsortien aus den Geistes- und Kulturwissenschaften, sowie Geo- und Lebenswissenschaften gelingen

Community Cluster:
Semantic Modelling & LOD

TRAILS

NFDI4
Objects

TWG

Community Cluster

NFDI lebt von der aktiven Mitarbeit

Interdisziplinäre Knowledge Graphen

Wie erreichen wir das?

**Zur Implementierung der Datenhomogenisierung
und Vernetzung von NFDI4Objects-Daten ...**

... mit Anschlussfähigkeit an die anderen konsortialen Knowledge Graphen ...

... dient die Erstellung eines gemeinsamen Minimal-Objekt-Metadatensets (N40 MMDS) und einer dazugehörigen Objekt-Ontologie (N40 OO).

NFDI4Objects

Knowledge Graph

Research Data Life Cycle

FAIRification Services

Object Biography

V. Liebler, F. Thiery, F.F. Schäfer, H. Senst, D. Wintergrün, CC BY-SA 4.0

FAIR Object Biography

F. Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Der N40 MMDS und die N40 OO bilden den Objektzyklus, der sukzessive durch die NFDI4Objects Task Areas mit den Aufgaben **documenting, collecting, analysing und protecting** mit Informationen angereichert wird, ab.

via <https://nfdi4objects.github.io/n4o-graph/architecture.html>, Stand 22.08.2024

**Diese Strukturen werden genutzt, da der Datenfluss
in den Knowledge Graphen des Konsortiums
LIDO/XML und RDF vorsieht**

**Little Minions, FAIRification Tools,
wie das SPARQLing Unicorn Plugin ...**

SPARQL Unicorn Ontology Documentation

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.8190763](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8190763)

This repository hosts a standalone version of the HTML documentation feature included in the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin.

Rather than initiating the documentation generation within the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin, this python script allows the generation of the documentation standalone or as a Github Action.

The standalone script does not rely on QGIS classes and does not provide the full functionality available in the SPARQLUnicorn QGIS Plugin.

Deviations from the SPARQLing Unicorn Plugin are listed as follows:

- Support for less geometry literals: Only WKT and GeoJSON literals are supported for rendering

Usage Example as Github Action

For a usage example please refer to this repository: https://github.com/sparqlunicorn/sparqlunicornGoesGIS_testdata

image via https://archaeolink-lod.github.io/ars/ic_8703dc7e-579e-48f0-a102-bac259527763/index.html

archaeology.link African Red Slip Ware (ARS) Linked Open Data | powered by Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie (LEIZA), Department of Scientific IT

bowl with Pan 🌐

http://data.archaeology.link/data/ars/ic_8703dc7e-579e-48f0-a102-bac259527763

The bowl with Pan resource is powered by Static GeoPubly generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Search Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL)

Property	Value
isShownAs	Information Carrier (InformationCarrier)
uri	http://data.archaeology.link/data/ars/ic_8703dc7e-579e-48f0-a102-bac259527763
isPartOf	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ars:11111111 ars:11111111 ars:11111111
isA	ars:11111111
hasShape	ars:11111111
hasColor	ars:11111111
hasMaterial	ars:11111111
hasHeight	ars:11111111
hasWidth	ars:11111111
hasDepth	ars:11111111
hasVolume	ars:11111111
hasMass	ars:11111111
hasWeight	ars:11111111
hasLength	ars:11111111
hasRadius	ars:11111111
hasDiameter	ars:11111111
hasCircumference	ars:11111111
hasArea	ars:11111111
hasPerimeter	ars:11111111

Metadata

Property	Value
identifier	ars:11111111
isPartOf	ars:11111111
isA	ars:11111111
hasShape	ars:11111111
hasColor	ars:11111111
hasMaterial	ars:11111111
hasHeight	ars:11111111
hasWidth	ars:11111111
hasDepth	ars:11111111
hasVolume	ars:11111111
hasMass	ars:11111111
hasWeight	ars:11111111
hasLength	ars:11111111
hasRadius	ars:11111111
hasDiameter	ars:11111111
hasCircumference	ars:11111111
hasArea	ars:11111111
hasPerimeter	ars:11111111

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image via https://archaeolink-lod.github.io/ars/feat_7e66a1b3-6c9b-4679-8c79-fdb4131b8429/index.html

archaeology.link African Red Slip Ware (ARS) Linked Open Data | powered by Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie (LEIZA), Department of Scientific IT

Löwenstein Pan II 🌐

http://data.archaeology.link/data/ars/ic_31a71348-d833-4880-b253-5d7ab007e73

The Löwenstein Pan II resource is powered by Static GeoPubly generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Search Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL)

Property	Value
isShownAs	Information Carrier (InformationCarrier)
uri	http://data.archaeology.link/data/ars/ic_31a71348-d833-4880-b253-5d7ab007e73
isPartOf	ars:11111111
isA	ars:11111111
hasShape	ars:11111111
hasColor	ars:11111111
hasMaterial	ars:11111111
hasHeight	ars:11111111
hasWidth	ars:11111111
hasDepth	ars:11111111
hasVolume	ars:11111111
hasMass	ars:11111111
hasWeight	ars:11111111
hasLength	ars:11111111
hasRadius	ars:11111111
hasDiameter	ars:11111111
hasCircumference	ars:11111111
hasArea	ars:11111111
hasPerimeter	ars:11111111

Metadata

Property	Value
identifier	ars:11111111
isPartOf	ars:11111111
isA	ars:11111111
hasShape	ars:11111111
hasColor	ars:11111111
hasMaterial	ars:11111111
hasHeight	ars:11111111
hasWidth	ars:11111111
hasDepth	ars:11111111
hasVolume	ars:11111111
hasMass	ars:11111111
hasWeight	ars:11111111
hasLength	ars:11111111
hasRadius	ars:11111111
hasDiameter	ars:11111111
hasCircumference	ars:11111111
hasArea	ars:11111111
hasPerimeter	ars:11111111

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... und das SPARQL Unicorn Ontology Documentation Tool können zudem dabei helfen, die für den Knowledge Graphen benötigten RDF-Daten zu visualisieren ...

... und für den Menschen lesbar,
z.B. in GIS bereitzustellen.

Austauschformate sind die Basis

- XML-Schema für **Austausch und normierte Erfassung** von **Objektinformationen**
- Aggregation von Daten des kulturellen Erbes (harvesting format)
- basiert auf CIDOC CRM, CDWA (Categories for the description of works of art) und Spectrum
- Nur wenige Pflichtelemente, daher verschiedene Anwendungsprofile
- Bestandteile
 - Metadaten zum Objekt
 - Metadaten zur Reproduktionen/Repräsentationen
 - Administrative Metadaten
- LIDO Terminologien (Wertelisten)
- Webseite: <https://cidoc.mini.icom.museum/working-groups/lido/lido-overview/>


```

<lido:lido>
  <lido:lidoRecID lido:type="xxx"></lido:lidoRecID>
  <lido:descriptiveMetadata xml:lang="xxx">
    <lido:objectClassificationWrap>
      <lido:objectWorkTypeWrap>
        <lido:objectWorkType></lido:objectWorkType>
      </lido:objectWorkTypeWrap>
    </lido:objectClassificationWrap>
    <lido:objectIdentificationWrap>
      <lido:titleWrap>
        <lido:titleSet>
          <lido:appellationValue>
            </lido:appellationValue>
          </lido:titleSet>
        </lido:titleWrap>
      </lido:objectIdentificationWrap>
    </lido:descriptiveMetadata>
    <lido:administrativeMetadata xml:lang="xxx">
      <lido:recordWrap>
        <lido:recordID lido:type="xxx"></lido:recordID>
        <lido:recordType></lido:recordType>
        <lido:recordSource></lido:recordSource>
      </lido:recordWrap>
    </lido:administrativeMetadata>
  </lido:lido>

```

Lightweight Information Describing Objects

- entwickelt, um u. a. im Bereich des Digitalen Kulturerbes ein Instrument für Standardisierung zu schaffen
- Daten stammen aus
 - verschiedenen Sammlungen / Objektklassen
 - verschiedenen Datenstrukturen
 - unterschiedlichen Softwaresystemen
- Ziel: Informationen außerhalb des eigenen Sammlungskontextes verständlich machen
- Vereinheitlichung heterogener Daten
- sinnvoll zur Orientierung, welche Metadaten erfasst werden sollten → Orientierungshilfe für Metadatenschema

Quelle: Klassik Stiftung Weimar

Lightweight Information Describing Objects

- URIs (Uniform Resource Identifier) verwenden
 - → Daten für Anwendungen des Semantic Web und als Linked (Open) Data zur Verfügung stellen
- wenn Vokabulare verwendet werden, Angabe der jeweiligen Identifier für eindeutige Zuordnung
- Je mehr Referenzen auf kontrollierte Vokabulare und Normdaten zur Verfügung stehen, desto mehr Begriffe für einen Sucheinstieg
- Grundprinzip Zuordnung einzelner Informationen zu **Ereignissen**, die einem Objekt widerfahren können

Quelle: Klassik Stiftung Weimar,
https://ores.klassik-stiftung.de/ords/ksw_internet/r/300/2?p2_ident=337945&p2_dateiname=100-2018-1557

Lightweight Information Describing Objects

KSW Museumsdatenbank (Version 24.2.1.0) [Produktivdatenbank]

Aktuelles Suchergebnis... 1 von 2

Übersicht

341013 GNG 04126

341016 GNG 04129

Inventarnummer: GNG 04126
 Bestand: Naturwissenschaftliche Sammlung Sammlungen
 Objektstatus: Inventar
 Standort: Goethe Nationalmuseum / Nationalmuseum / 2. Obergeschoss / Naturwissenschaftliches Kabinett / Schrank XVIII / Schub 3
 erfasst durch: Vor Konvertierung
 erfasst am:
 bearbeitet durch: KRISTINA JOHANNES
 bearbeitet am: 06.06.2023 17:08:15

Präsentationstitel: Suite geschliffener Gesteine aus Italien, E13. Creduto Plasma.
 Personen / Körperschaften: Sammler: Goethe, Johann Wolfgang von (1749 - 1832)
 Datierung

Kerndaten Katalogdaten technische Daten Erwerb & Provenienz / Rechte Ausstellungen Export Digitalisate Pre-Migrationsdaten

Personen / Körperschaften
 Sammler: Goethe, Johann Wolfgang von (1749 - 1832) 2475 Status

Datierung / Stil
 <Keine Daten anzuzeigen>

Titel / Bezeichnung
 Präsentationstitel alt: Suite geschliffener Gesteine aus Italien, E13. Creduto Plasma.
 Gegenstand alt: Suite geschliffener Gesteine aus Italien, E13. Creduto Plasma.

Orte
 <Keine Daten anzuzeigen>

Kategorie:
 /Werkstoff, Substanz, Rohstoff*
 /Werkstoff, Substanz, Rohstoff*/Mineral

Schlagerworte
 GND

Digitalisate - Museen
 Museen

freigeschaltete Digitalisate

Präsentationstexte
 Texte Autor Jahr +
 <Keine Daten anzuzeigen>

Material / Technik extern
 Status

Maße
 Objektmaß Höhe: 0,7 cm; Breite: 7,4 cm; Läng: +

technische Daten

Standort (wie Online-Anzeige)

Restaurierung / Depot

Screenshot aus der Museumsdatenbank der Klassik Stiftung Weimar, einer eigenentwickelten Oracle-Datenbank

Informationen, die in Erfassungsumgebungen oft in einem einem Feld zusammengefasst sind, werden in LIDO auf mehrere Elemente aufgeteilt und / oder mit verschiedenen Attributen versehen → Präzisierung und Kontextualisierung

Lightweight Information Describing Objects

The screenshot shows the XML Editor interface with the following components:

- Projekt:** A tree view on the left showing a project structure with folders like 'css', 'debugger', 'epub', 'fo', 'import', 'json', 'jsp', 'nvd', 'relaxng', 'schematron', and 'svg'. A message states 'Die Hauptdatei-Unterstützung ist deaktiviert.' with 'Aktivieren' and 'Mehr lesen' buttons.
- Gliederung:** A 'Elementnamen-Filter' section below the project view, listing elements like 'lido:lido', 'lido:lidoRecID', 'lido:descriptiveMetadata', and 'lido:administrativeMetadata'.
- Main Editor:** A large text area displaying XML code for a LIDO record. The code includes elements such as <lido:lido>, <lido:lidoRecID>, <lido:descriptiveMetadata>, <lido:objectClassificationWrap>, <lido:objectWorkTypeWrap>, <lido:term>, <lido:conceptID>, <lido:objectWorkType>, <lido:appellationValue>, <lido:repositoryWrap>, <lido:workID>, <lido:recordWrap>, <lido:recordID>, <lido:recordType>, <lido:conceptID>, <lido:term>, <lido:recordSource>, <lido:legalBodyID>, <lido:legalBodyName>, <lido:appellationValue>, <lido:recordRights>, <lido:rightsType>, and <lido:conceptID>.
- Footer:** A status bar at the bottom showing the file path 'C:\Users\anja.gerber\Desktop\creduto_plasma.xml', a message 'Das Dokument ist wohlgeformt.', and user/line information 'U+0061 1:40'.

LIDO-Export des Datensatzes aus der MDB der Klassik Stiftung Weimar

Lightweight Information Describing Objects

- **Terminologien** sind Listen von **Konzepten** (Orte, Personen, Fächer, Materialien...) mit **persistenten Identifikatoren**, Namen und ggf. weiteren Angaben
- Ohne Verwendung gleicher **persistenter Identifikatoren** keine Interoperabilität!

Zwei mögliche “Kategorien” von Terminologien

- Normdateien, Thesauri, Klassifikationen, ...
- Ontologien und Datenformate

place: Frankfurt

Terminologien zur Sicherstellung von Interoperabilität

Terminologien in NFDIObjects und NFDI

Kontrollierte Vokabulare, die auch in anderen Bereichen etabliert sind, z.B.:

- Getty TGN / GeoNames / Pleiades (**Orte / Gazetteers**)
- PeriodO / ChronOntology (**Zeiträume**)
- GND / VIAF / ULAN / ORCID / ROR (**Personen / Körperschaften**)
- Getty AAT / IconClass / Wikidata (**Sachbegriffe u.A.**)

Speziellere Terminologien in NFDI4Objects:

- [Heritage Data Vocabularies](#) (Historic England/Scotland/Wales)
- Nomisma ([Ontologie](#) und [Vokabular](#)) für numismatische Daten
- Ceramic Typologies Ontology ([CeraTyOnt](#))
- Objektbezeichnungsdatei ([OBG](#))
- Fachklassifikationen: Ackerbau-Systematik, Möbeltypologie, Gefäßtypologie...
- Metadaten für Analyse-, Mess- und Labordaten

⇒ **basieren im Idealfall auf CIDOC-CRM oder SKOS**

Terminologien in NFDIObjects

Datenfelder (Erfassung)

Datenfelder, die üblicherweise bei der Erfassung befüllt werden:

- Objekttitle oder -benennung (Pflicht)
- Objekttyp oder -bezeichnung (Pflicht)
- Klassifikation (Empfohlen)
- Inventarnummer (Pflicht)
- Objektbeschreibung (Empfohlen)
- Material (Empfohlen)
- Technik (Empfohlen)
- Maße (Empfohlen)
- Ereignis in der Objektgeschichte [Feldgruppe] (Pflicht)
 - Ereignistyp (Pflicht)
 - Person/Körperschaft (Bedingt Pflicht)
 - Datierung (Bedingt Pflicht)
 - Ort (Bedingt Pflicht)
- Inhaltsschlagwort (Empfohlen)
- Mediendatei [Feldgruppe] (Pflicht)
 - Link zur Mediendatei (Pflicht)
 - Nutzungsrechte Mediendatei (Pflicht)
 - Rechtswahrnehmung Mediendatei (Bedingt Pflicht)
 - Alternativtext (Empfohlen)

www.minimaldatensatz.de

Datenfelder (Export)

Datenfelder, die üblicherweise erst beim oder nach dem Export aus dem lokalen Datenbanksystem befüllt werden:

- ID Datensatz (Pflicht)
- Sprache des Datensatzes (Pflicht)
- Datensatzart (Pflicht)
- Verwahrende Einrichtung (Pflicht)
- Datensatzerstellende Einrichtung (Pflicht)
- Mediendatei: Medientyp (Pflicht)
- Nutzungsrechte Metadaten (Pflicht)
- Link zum veröffentlichten Metadatensatz (Empfohlen)
- Datierung des Datensatzes (Empfohlen)

Minimaldatensatz-Empfehlung der DDB für Museen und Sammlungen

```
<lido:objectIdentificationWrap>
  <lido:titleWrap>
    <lido:titleSet lido:type="http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300417200">
      <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="de">Vier tanzende Musen</lido:appellationValue>
    </lido:titleSet>
    <lido:titleSet lido:type="http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300417227">
      <lido:appellationValue xml:lang="de">Tanzende Göttinnen</lido:appellationValue>
    </lido:titleSet>
  </lido:titleWrap>
</lido:objectIdentificationWrap>
```

Quelle: www.minimaldatensatz.de

Vergleich mit einschlägigen Standards und Datenbankmodellen

Standard	Elementname	Text/URI	Wiederholbar	Verpflichtungsgrad	Kommentar
DDB: Anforderungen an die Lieferdaten	Objekttitel	Text	Ja	Pflicht	
Anwendungsprofil DDB-LIDO	<titleWrap>	Text	Ja	Pflicht	Wenn mehrere Titel geliefert werden, müssen diese typisiert und welche die weiteren Titel sind. Der bevorzugte Titel type http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300417200 oder http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300417227 für "Alternativer Originaltitel"
DFG-Basisdatensatz	Titel Ausgangsobjekt	Text	Keine Angabe	Pflicht	
DFG-Praxisregeln Digitalisierung: LIDO-Kernmetadaten	Titel/Objektname <titleSet>	Text	Ja	Pflicht	
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	<dc:title>	Text	Ja	Bedingt Pflicht	Im Europeana Data Model sind <dc:title> (Objekttitel)
EODEM-Anwendungsprofil	Title/Name /lido:titleWrap/ lido:titleSet/lido:appellationValue	Text	Nein	Pflicht	Zusätzlich sind im EODEM-Anwendungsprofil die Elemente verpflichtend.
digiCULT	Titel / Objektname	Text	Ja	Empfohlen	digiCULT bietet die Möglichkeit, den Titel zu typisieren und die Unterscheidung verschiedener Titelarten zu gewährleisten.
museum-digital	Objektname	Text	Ja	Pflicht	

Minimaldatensatz-Empfehlung der DDB für Museen und Sammlungen

Ontologien als Basis

- Abstraktes Datenmodell mit Schwerpunkt auf Informationen zum kulturellen Erbe
- Entstehung etwa parallel zu Dublin Core in den 1990ern
- Eher indirekte Nutzung als Grundlage für eigene Modellierung (Referenzmodell)
- Möglichen Kodierung in XML, RDF... (also auch als RDF-Ontologie)
- **Ereigniszentrierte** Datenerfassung
- Dokumentiert unter <https://www.cidoc-crm.org/>
- besteht aus ca. 90 Klassen (**E5** Event, **E11** Modification, **E18** Physical Thing, **E39** Actor, ...)
und ca. 150 Eigenschaften (**P4** has time-span, **P45** consists of...)
- 11 offizielle Erweiterungen, z.B. **CRMarchaeo**, **CRMba**, **CRMdig**
- **Version 7.1.3** ist ISO-zertifiziert (ISO 21127) und bildet die Basis für die Entwicklungen in NFDI4Objects

Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC CRM)

The **PROV Ontology** (PROV-O) defines the OWL2 Web Ontology Language encoding of the PROV Data Model. The ontology specification provides the foundation to implement **provenance applications in different domains that can represent, exchange, and integrate provenance information generated in different systems and under different contexts.**

Provenance Ontology (PROV-O)

from <https://basic-formal-ontology.org/>

The **Basic Formal Ontology (BFO)** is a small, upper level ontology that is **designed for use in supporting information retrieval, analysis and integration in scientific and other domains**. BFO is a genuine upper ontology. Thus it does not contain physical, chemical, biological or other terms which would properly fall within the coverage domains of the special sciences. BFO is used by more than 550 ontology-driven endeavors throughout the world.

The BFO project was initiated in 2002 under the auspices of the project Forms of Life sponsored by the Volkswagen Foundation. The theory behind BFO was developed first by Barry Smith and Pierre Grenon.

Basic Formal Ontology (BFO)

from <https://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core/guide/2005-10-06/>

from <https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-primer/>

SKOS – Simple Knowledge Organization System – provides a model for expressing the basic structure and content of concept schemes such as thesauri, classification schemes, subject heading lists, taxonomies, folksonomies, and other similar types of controlled vocabulary. As an application of the Resource Description Framework (RDF), SKOS allows concepts to be composed and published on the World Wide Web, linked with data on the Web and integrated into other concept schemes.

Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS)

via <http://www.openqgis.net/doc/IS/geosparql/1.1>,
 Nicholas J. Car, Timo Homburg et al. (2024)

via <https://pleiades.stoa.org/help/pleiades-data-model>

GeoSPARQL and Pleiades Ontology

from <https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-primer/>

from <https://www.w3.org/TR/annotation-model/>

Annotations are typically used to convey information about a resource or associations between resources. Simple examples include a comment or tag on a single web page or image, or a blog post about a news article.

The **Web Annotation Data Model** specification describes a **structured model and format to enable annotations to be shared and reused across different hardware and software platforms**. Common use cases can be modeled in a manner that is simple and convenient, while at the same time enabling more complex requirements, including linking arbitrary content to a particular data point or to segments of timed multimedia resources.

from Oscar Díaz, Haritz Medina, Felipe I. Anfurrutia (2019):
“Coding-Data Portability in Systematic Literature Reviews:
a W3C’s Open Annotation Approach”
10.1145/3319008.3319025

Web Annotation Data Model

The National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) initiative has seen the establishment of various consortia, each dedicated to developing a research data infrastructure tailored to its respective domain. To facilitate **interoperability** across these consortia, the **NFDIcore ontology** has been developed and serves as a **mid level ontology for representing metadata about NFDI resources such as individuals, organizations, projects, data portals, etc.**

Recognizing the diverse needs of consortia, NFDIcore establishes mappings to a wide array of standards across domains, including the Basic Formal Ontology (BFO) and schema.org, which is crucial for advancing knowledge representation, data exchange, and collaboration across diverse domains.

NFDI Core Ontology

Linked Archaeological Data Ontology

Revision:
v1.0

Authors:
[Florian Thiery](#)

Publisher:
[Florian Thiery](#), RGZM (LEIZA)

Download serialization:

[Format JSON LD](#) [Format RDF/XML](#) [Format N Triples](#) [Format TTL](#)

License:

License [CC BY 4.0](#)

Visualization:

[Visualize with WebVowl](#)

[Provenance of this page](#)

Linked Archaeological Data Ontology (LADO)

Geistes- und kulturwissenschaftliche Konsortien
in der NFDI

**Abstimmung der Entwicklungen der Ontologien auf Ebene der Memorandumsgruppe, um Anschlussfähigkeit sicherzustellen;
erfolgt unter Beteiligung aller in die Entwicklung von Ontologien und Wissensgraphen beteiligten Mitarbeitenden;
Umsetzung anhand konkreter Use Cases**

Use Cases

LIDO Framework

```

<lido:titleWrap>
  <lido:titleSet lido:type="generated_short" lido:sortorder="1">
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      Nominal, Datierung
      Münzstand
      Münzherr
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```

```

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  </lido:titleSet>
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```

LIDO-Datenmodell mit Schwerpunkt auf Münzdaten, entwickelt von Timo Schleier, VZG
 → Anpassungen an LIDO-Datenexport notwendig,

Quelle: https://dokumentation.digitalebibliothek.gbv.de/kenom:Kenom_Export_Format_-_descriptiveMetadata

KENOM

© Klassik Stiftung Weimar, Museen

Material / Technik

Silberlegierung

Objektmaß(e)

Gewicht: 30,7844 g; Stempelstellung: 12 h; Länge: 59 mm; Breite: 58,9 mm

Kategorie

Münze

Inventarnummer

MM-2022/4821

Standort / aktuelle Ausstellung

derzeit nicht ausgestellt

Creditline

Klassik Stiftung Weimar, Museen

Literatur / Quellen

unbek. - 1911 - Inventarband X Sachsen. A. Münzen der Ernestinischen Linie

Provenienz

1844 (Zugangsdatum), Alter Besitz, Großherzogliche Bibliothek, Soret
1927 (), Übernahme, Staatliche Kunstsammlungen zu Weimar, Thüringische Landesbibliothek

Rechtehinweise ►

Quelle: https://ores.klassik-stiftung.de/ords/ksw_internet/r/300/2?p2_ident=692480&p2_dateiname=692480_VIS_VS

Goethes Münzsammlung an der Klassik Stiftung Weimar umfasst ca. 24.000 Datensätze. Die Sammlung wird mit Metadaten annotiert und für eine Portallieferung an KENOM nach LIDO konvertiert.

KLASSIK
STIFTUNG
WEIMAR

Ein Problem melden

Bestände durchsuchen

Wir möchten in unserer Online Collection Zugang zu möglichst vielen Objekten bieten. Die Ergänzung vertiefender Informationen und die Einarbeitung aktueller Forschungsergebnisse sind unser Ziel und ein fortlaufender Prozess. Ihre Anregungen und Kommentare sind dabei eine wertvolle Unterstützung. Bitte nutzen Sie dafür die Feedbackfunktion an den einzelnen Objektdatensätzen.

Titel:
Mineralien-Sammlung, Bergkristalldruse aus der Dauphinée

Datenbestand:
Klassik Stiftung Weimar
Sammlungen der Museen

Inventarnummer:
GNG 00118

Objektsystematik:
Naturwissenschaften

Personen / Körperschaften:
Goethe, Johann Wolfgang von (1749 - 1832) | Sammler

Sammlungsbereich:
Naturwissenschaftliche Sammlung

Feedback?

Weitere Objekte der Museen (nach Bildähnlichkeit):

- Gesteins-Sammlung, (Al...
- Mineralien-Sammlung, ...
- Gesteins-Sammlung, Ro...

1 of 1 • 1

Die vielfältigen, directionsübergreifenden Bestände an der Klassik Stiftung Weimar werden mit Metadaten annotiert und brauchen ein gemeinsames Austauschformat zur Durchsuchbarkeit (orientiert an Dublin Core und schema.org).

Link zum Datensatz: [https://ores.klassik-stiftung.de/ords/ksw_internet/r/300/2?p2_ident=1808&p2_dateiname=1808_\(3049702881\)](https://ores.klassik-stiftung.de/ords/ksw_internet/r/300/2?p2_ident=1808&p2_dateiname=1808_(3049702881))

Detailsansicht

creating new dimensions ABOUT EVENTS DATASETS PROJEKTE FAQ

HOUDON-BÜSTEN IN 3D

Zwei Highlights aus den „Digitalen Sammlungen der Museen“ der Klassik Stiftung Weimar

Klassik Stiftung Weimar, Museen

Datenzugang

- Datenset „Christoph Willibald Ritter von Gluck“ bei Radar4Culture: <https://doi.org/10.22000/747>
- Datenset „Sophie Arnould als Iphigenie“ bei Radar4Culture: <https://doi.org/10.22000/748>
- Datensets bei Sketchfab

Personen & Körperschaften

Houdon, Jean Antoine (1741 - 1828) [so:fie](#)

Künstler

Arnould, Sophie (1740 - 1802) [so:fie](#)

dargestellte Person

Titel

Arnould, Sophie (1744-1802) als Iphigenie

Datierung

1775

Material / Technik

Gipsabguss, gefasst

Kategorie

Büste

Inventarnummer

KPI/00253

Standort / aktuelle Ausstellung

derzeit nicht ausgestellt

Creditline

Sketchfab EXPLORE BUY 3D MODELS FOR BUSINESS Search 3D models

Sophie Arnould als Iphigenie
3D Model

[digitus.art](#) [PRO](#)
FOLLOW

Download 3D Model + Add To </> Embed ↗ Share

Triangles: 326.4k Vertices: 163.2k [More model information](#)

NoAI: This model may not be used in datasets for, in the development of, or as inputs to generative AI programs. [Learn more](#)

Titel: "Arnould, Sophie (1744-1802) als Iphigenie"
Künstler: Houdon, Jean Antoine (1741 - 1828)
Datierung: 1775
Eigentümer: Klassik Stiftung Weimar, Museen

Die vielfältigen, directionsübergreifenden Bestände an der Klassik Stiftung Weimar werden mit Metadaten annotiert und brauchen ein gemeinsames Austauschformat zur Durchsuchbarkeit und für Datenlieferungen an Portale, die oft LIDO benötigen.

Maske

[@ Kontakt](#) [Merken](#) [Teilen](#)

Zu den wertvollsten Stücken der Benin-Sammlung gehört diese Miniaturmaske aus Elfenbein. Weltweit gibt es nur ca. 4 Vergleichsstücke. Sie wurde als ein Ahnenobjekt über Jahrhunderte geehrt und gehütet. Dargestellt ist die Königinmutter ("lyoba") Idia, Mutter des 17. Oba Esigie (amtierte 1504–1550). Die Königinmütter hatten generell eine sehr starke und unabhängige Stellung im Königreich. Sie erzogen den künftigen König, lebten nach dessen Inthronisierung aber in einem eigenen Palast. Der amtierende Oba durfte keinen direkten Kontakt unterhalten und holte ihren Rat über Dritte ein. Manche, wie insbesondere die hochverehrte Idia, traten auch als große Heerführerinnen in Erscheinung. Idia sicherte so die Herrschaft ihres Sohnes gegen Gegner im Inneren wie Äußeren. Dabei war ihr politischer Rat ebenso wichtig, wie ihre...

[Mehr lesen](#) ▾

Datenpartner

Linden-Museum Stuttgart Staatliches Museum
für Völkerkunde[Original beim Datenpartner anzeigen](#)

Erschließungsdaten

Kulturelle Zuschreibung

Edo

Objekttyp

Maske

Maße

Breite: 10 cm; Höhe: 21 cm

DDB-LIDO am Beispiel des CCC-Portals für Sammlungsgut aus kolonialen Kontexten der Deutschen Digitalen Bibliothek

Maske | Fotograf*in: Anatol Dreyer

© 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24 25 26 27 28 29 30 31 32 33 34 35 36 37 38 39 40 41 42 43 44 45 46 47 48 49 50 51 52 53 54 55 56 57 58 59 60 61 62 63 64 65 66 67 68 69 70 71 72 73 74 75 76 77 78 79 80 81 82 83 84 85 86 87 88 89 90 91 92 93 94 95 96 97 98 99 100

Herstellung		^
wann	16. Jahrhundert	
Quelle(n)	Archiv Linden-Museum, Liste 2405, Dok. Antrag Hans Rhotert an das Kultusministerium Baden-Württemberg, 19.03.1964, Betreff: Antrag auf Erwerb einer Elfenbeinmaske aus Benin (Südnigeria); Jürgen Zwernemann, Die Benin-Maske des Linden-Museums, in: Tribus 14 (1965), S. 149-159.	
Besitzwechsel: Plünderung		^
wann	1897	
wo	Königreich Benin	
Beschreibung	Nach Aussage von Rhotert und Pitt Rivers wurde die Maske bei der Erstürmung von Benin-Stadt versteckt in einer Eichenkiste in dem Schlafsaal des Königs Ovonramwen Nogbaisi (ca.1850-1914) gefunden.	
Quelle(n)	Archiv Linden-Museum, Liste 2405, Dok. Antrag Hans Rhotert an das Kultusministerium Baden-Württemberg, 19.03.1964, Betreff: Antrag auf Erwerb einer Elfenbeinmaske aus Benin (Südnigeria); Augustus Pitt Rivers, Antique Works of Art from Benin. [Privatdruck – London], 1900, S. 12 und Taf. VI, Fig. 25 u. 26.	
Besitzwechsel: Auktion	↑	∨

DDB-LIDO am Beispiel des CCC-Portals für Sammlungsgut aus kolonialen Kontexten der Deutschen Digitalen Bibliothek

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DDB LIDO am Beispiel des CCC-Portals

- Personal Names
- Titles
- People
- Inscribed Objects
- Places
- Collections
- Name Types
- Bibliography
- Info

Inscribed Objects

You can use % or * as wildcards when searching for titles or inventory numbers. Thus, "CG 2011*" will match all stelae from "CG 20110" to "CG 20119". Inventory numbers are searched for when a collection is selected.

Collection: Title or inventory number:

Type
 Material
 Size
 Content
 Script
 Region
 Period

Type
 Object type:
 Subtype:

Size
 less than or equal to / **greater than or equal to**
 Largest dimension in mm

Displaying inscriptions 1 – 50 out of 21909

Type	Object	Material	Size, mm	Text	Date	Provenance	Or
Statue	À l'école des scribes, no. B.25	basalt	170	Formula HDN	Middle Kingdom and Second Intermediate Period		
Stela	AB.NEG AB_25_0186			Formula HDN	Middle Kingdom and Second Intermediate Period	Abydos	
Block	AB.NEG AB_25_0191 (S.42)			Name	13th Dyn., ca. Senbi	Abydos	
Block	AB.NEG AB_25_0192 (S.37)			Formula HDN	13th Dyn., ca. Senbi	Abydos	
Tomb equipment	Abdel Fatah, Bickel, BIFAO 100, 3-10			Funerary text	FIP - Senusret I	Sedment	
Tomb equipment	Abdel Fatah, Bickel, BIFAO 100, 10-13			Funerary text	FIP - Senusret I	Sedment	
Tomb equipment	Abdel Fatah, Bickel, BIFAO 100, 13-17			Funerary text	FIP - Senusret I	Sedment	
Statue	Abdel Maksoud, Valbelle, RdE 56, 7-8, fig. 5 (7)	limestone	430	Name	not earlier than Amenemhat IV	Tell Hebua	
Stela	Abdel Maksoud, Valbelle, RdE 56, 8-11, fig. 6		650	Royal text	Nehsy 9-sty-r	Tell Hebua	
Stela	Aberdeen ABDUA:15651	sandstone		Formula HDN	SIP		Elk
Statue	Aberdeen ABDUA:21459	basalt	175	Formula HDN	18th Dyn. before Amenhotep IV	Elephantine	
Statue	Aberdeen ABDUA:21460	basalt	169	Formula HDN	18th Dyn. before Amenhotep IV		

Prosopographia
Memphitica

GENERAL INFORMATION

ID: 85

Type: stela

Subtype 1: round-topped stela

Subtype 2: not recorded

TECHNICAL DATA

Material: limestone

Length [cm]: 155

Width [cm]: 90

Height [cm]: 11-17

DATING

After Dynasty: NK, Dyn 18-19

After king: Horemheb-Sety I

After regnal years: 1319-1279 BC

Holder: Rijksmuseum van Oudheden
Credits: Rijksmuseum van Oudheden, Leiden, AP 8

Beispiel oben: Screenshot der Datenbank **Persons and names of the Middle Kingdom** von Alexander Ilin-Tomich, <https://pnm.uni-mainz.de/>.

Beispiel rechts: Anne Herzberg-Beiersdorf, **Prosopographia Memphitica**, <https://anneherz.github.io/ProM/>, Datensatz rechts: https://www.prosopographia-memphitica.com/ProM/detail/singleview_objects.html?ids=85.

Entwicklung eines LIDO-Anwendungsprofils für archäologische Daten in NFDI4Objects zusammen mit der deutschen LIDO AG anhand konkreter Forschungsprojekte

Use Cases

Ontologien

Paradigmen

The “Trinity” - Place / Time / Actor (Object)

via <https://pleiades.stoa.org/help/pleiades-data-model>

Places

Pleiades places are the primary organizational construct of the gazetteer. They are conceptual entities: the term "place" applies to any locus of human attention, material or intellectual, in a real-world geographic context. A settlement mentioned in an ancient text is a place, whether or not it can now be located; an archaeological site is a place; a modern city located atop an ancient settlement is a place. Basically, any spatial feature that is connected to the pre-modern past and that a human being has noticed and discussed as such between the past and the present is a place.

Locations

Locations in Pleiades connect places to coordinates in space. A location identifies a specific area of interest on the earth's surface that is associated with a place during a particular date range. A place can contain multiple locations. Locations, on the other hand, are associated with one and only one place. Depending on the state of the evidence, the association between location and place may vary in certainty; some places, attested by name in ancient sources, may have no associated location at all because modern scholarship cannot pinpoint reliably the ancient site or area in question.

via <https://pleiades.stoa.org/help/conceptual-overview>

→ Rabinowitz, Adam. „It's about Time: Historical Periodization and Linked Ancient World Data“. In ISAW Papers 7.22, 2014. <http://dlib.nyu.edu/awdl/isaw/isaw-papers/7/rabinowitz/>

via <https://rgzm.github.io/samian-lod/doc/#detailed-actor>

Actor

Time

K.C. Bruhn, CC BY 4.0

Time Geography

Zeitkonzept

Event

Georeferencing

via gu.se

Place / Actor / Time / Event as a Concept

- Konzept der Biografie auf materielle Kulturgüter übertragen
- Kompilation jeglicher Information (Kontexte, Wege, Bedeutungen, Deutungen) zu einem Objekt
- **Objekte** (Artefakte, Pflanzen, Tiere, Gesteine)
- **Phasen und Kontexte**
 - Entstehungsangaben
 - Benutzung
 - Begegnung
 - Sammlungskontext
 - Besitz-/Eigentumswechsel
 - Rezeption, Forschungsereignisse
- **Akteure, Orte, Zeit** (wer? wo? wann? Kontext?)
- **Quellen** (Bild- und Schriftgut, Daten, Befunde, ...)

Darstellung: Sarah Wagner, CC BY 4.0

Objektbiografien in NFDI4Objects

E5 Event
 E7 Activity
 E6 Destruction
 E12 Production
 E22 Human-Made Object
 E63 Beginning of Existence
 E65 Creation

nach "NFDI4Objects Core Ontology und Objektbiografien",
 S. Wagner, A. Gerber, CC BY 4.0, via DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10591897.

Kontextualisierung der Objektinformation

E12 Production
E22 Human-Made Object
E39 Actor
E52 Time Span
E53 Place
E63 Beginning of Existence

Kontextualisierung der Objektinformation

E12 Production
E22 Human-Made Object
E13 Attribute Assignment
E63 Beginning of Existence

Kontextualisierung der Objektinformation

E13 Attribute Assignment
E21 Person
E39 Group
E40 Legal Body

E73 [Information Object] Zuweisung von konkreten Informationen in Verbindung mit der Quelle, aus der sie stammen.

Kontextualisierung der Objektinformation

Use Cases

CIDOC CRM

... in Online-Datenbanken

Samian Research / LEIZA

Samian Research ID	118117	Decoration Nr.		OCK Vessel Nr.	
Tradition	Gaulish-Germanic-Raetian	OCK Potter Nr.		Die position	Base inside
Kilnsite	Kräherwald and Rheinzabern	Special Reading	QVETVSF	Simple Reading	Pro
Potter	Quietus (Quetus) (About)	Reading Direction		Slip colour	
Die	34 (Graph Die Variety of Quietus (Quetus))	Site	Köngen (9.366666, 48.833334) #Places id 118706	Findspot	Grabung 1882, cemetery
Frame No	0 info	Repository site	Stuttgart	Museum Inv. No.	R.102.14
Date	AD 155-180	Repository	Württembergisches Landesmuseum	Excavation Nr.	
Form	15/17 or 18 or 18/31 (Disk) There are 10.26% (1946 out of 18961) 15/17 There are 48.57% (9210 out of 18961) 18 There are 41.16% (7805 out of 18961) 18/31	Amount	1	Bibliography	Luik 1996, Taf.150, 441
		Comment			

Die Online-Datenbank Samian Research enthält 250'000+ Töpferstempel von 5000+ römischen Töpfern, deren Produkte im ganzen Römischen Reich gefunden werden

Samian Research Ontologie

- **Main Classes**

- samian:InformationCarrier (E22 Human-Made Object)
- samian:Inscription (E25 Human-Made Feature)
- samian:Potform (E55 Type)
- samian:Actor (Potter, E39 Actor / ActorAsAConcept)
- samian:InscriptionMakingType (Tool, E22 Human-Made Object)
- samian:Place (E53 Place / geo:SpatialObject / PlaceAsAConcept)
- samian:Location (E53 Place / geo:SpatialObject)
- samian:DiscoverySite (E53 Place / geo:SpatialObject)
- samian:KilnSite (E53 Place / geo:SpatialObject)

- **Main Properties**

- samian:carries (*subclass of P56 bears feature*) [IC→In]
- samian:representedBy (*subclass of P2 has type*) [IC→Pf]
- samian:isAbout (*subclass of P62 depicts*) [In→Ac]
- samian:wasMadeBy (*subclass of L20i was created by, via CRMdig*) [In→MT]
- samian:disclosedAt (*subclass of P53 has former or current location*) [IC→DS]
- samian:hasKilnsite (*subclass of P53 has former or current location*) [IC→KS]
- samian:worksAtPlace (*subclass of P53 has former or current location*) [Ac→KS]
- samian:hasPlace (*subclass of P53 has former or current location*) [In→P]
- samian:hasLocation (*subclass of P89 falls within*) [P→L]

* geo: <<http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>>

Samain Research in CIDOC CRM

Florian Thiery, Peter Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Irische Ogham-Steine mit Inschriften des primitive Irish Ogham Script

Fotos / Grafiken: Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0,
 via https://doi.org/10.17175/sb005_010

Ogham-Ontologie

- **Main Classes**

- oghamonto:**O**gham**S**tone (**E22** Human-Made Object)
- oghamonto:**O**gham**S**ite (**E53** Place / **geo:SpatialObject** / **PlaceAsAConcept**)
- oghamonto:**I**nscription (**E25** Human-Made Feature / **TX1** Written Text, via *CRMtex*)
- oghamonto:**R**eading (**E25** Human-Made Feature / **TX7** Written Text Segment, via *CRMtex*)
- oghamonto:**W**ord (**TX7** Written Text Segment / **E36** Visual Item)
- oghamonto:**P**erson (**E39** Actor / **E36** Visual Item / **ActorAsAConcept**)
- oghamonto:Townland/Barony/County/Province/State (**E53 Place** / **geo:SpatialObject**)

- **Main Properties**

- oghamonto:disclosedAt (*subclass* of **P53** has former or current location) [**OSt**→**OSi**]
- oghamonto:shows (*subclass* of **P138i** has representation) [**OSt**→**P/W**]
- oghamonto:carries (*subclass* of **P56** bears feature) [**IC**→**In**]
- oghamonto:identified as (*subclass* of **TXP4** has segment, via *CRMtex*) [**In**→**I**]
- oghamonto:within (*subclass* of **P89** falls within) [**Place**→**Place**]

CRMtex
Textual Entities Model

* geo: <<http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>>

Irish Ogham Stones in CIDOC CRM

Go to inscription

Ogham in 3D
English | Gaeilge

Introduction
Ogham
Alphabet
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CIIC 153. Ballinrannig VI (BAILE AN REANNAIGH), Co. Kerry

Download Epidoc | URI https://ogham.celt.dias.ie/153_Ballinrannig_VI

Inscription Description 3D View Map Epidoc

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<?oxygen RNGSchema="http://www.stoa.org/epidoc/schema/8.13/tei-epidoc.rng" type="xml"?>
<TEI xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0">
  <teiHeader>
    <fileDesc>
      <titleStm>
        <title>CIIC 153. Ballinrannig VI</title>
      </titleStm>
      <editor>
        <persName>Nora White</persName>
        <roleName>Principal Investigator</roleName>
        <orgName>Dublin Institute for Advanced Studies</orgName>
      </editor>
      <respStm>
        <resp>captured by the Corca Dhuibhne 3d community project (Helena Zacharias) in 2017 using photogrammetry and processed by Discovery Programme using Agisoft
        <name>Gary Devlin</name>
        <orgName>Discovery Programme</orgName>
      </respStm>
    </fileDesc>
    <publicationStm>
      < distributor>Dublin Institute for Advanced Studies</distributor>
      <pubPlace>Dublin</pubPlace>
      <availability><licence target="http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/3.0/ie/deed.en_us"><p>This work is licensed under the Creative Commons licence Attribution-NonCom
      <p>Copyright (c) 2013 by the School of Celtic Studies <ref>http://www.celt.dias.ie</ref></p>
      <p>All reuse or distribution of this work must contain somewhere a reference to <ref>http://ogham.celt.dias.ie/</ref></p>
      </licence></availability>
    </publicationStm>
    <sourceDesc>
      <p>Inscription originally published in < bibl>
        <title level="m" xml:lang="la">Corpus Inscriptionum Insularum
          Celticarum</title>
        <author>R.A.S. Macalister</author> (<date>1945</date>) </bibl>
      </p>
    </sourceDesc>
  </teiHeader>
  <fileDesc>
    <encodingDesc>
      <p>Marked-up according to the Epidoc Guidelines version 8.13
      in <date>May 2018</date>
      by
      <name>
        <persName>Nora White</persName>
        <roleName>Principal Investigator</roleName>
      </name></p>
    </encodingDesc>
    <projectDesc>
      <p>
        <title>Ogham in 3D</title> The ultimate aim of the Ogham in 3D project is to
        digitise and record in 3d as many as possible of the approximately four hundred surviving Ogham stones and to make
        these 3D models freely available on the <orgName>Dublin Institute for Advanced
        Studies</orgName> website as part of a multi-disciplinary archive of Ogham
        stones. </p>
    </projectDesc>
  </fileDesc>
</TEI>
```


TEI EPIDOC to (CIDOC-based) RDF?

via <https://linkedopenogham.github.io/o3d-epidoc-extractor/> on <https://github.com/linkedOpenOgham/o3d-epidoc-extractor/>

OGI Ogham Analyses

CC BY 4.0 Timo Homburg, Florian Thiery, data based on <http://ogham.celt.dias.ie> CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 Ireland, ©2013 by the School of Celtic Studies <http://www.celt.dias.ie>

TEI EPIDOC Example from Ogham in 3D

The screenshot shows a web application interface for Ogham data. It features a map of Ireland with various locations marked by colored pins. A popup window titled "Ogham Data (CIIC 178)" is open, displaying the following information:

- image - <http://webgis.archaeology.ie/HistoricEnvironment/?SMRS=KE052-059002->
- title - CIIC 178. Coumeenole
- textogham -
- Persons
 - DOVINIAS (
 - ERC (
 - MAQI-ERCIA (
- Father - Son
 - ERC (
 is son of MAQI-ERCIA (

- id - CIIC 178
- text - ERC MAQI MAQI-ERCIA MUOI? DOVINIAS

Below the map is a legend with various icons and their corresponding Ogham names and meanings:

- All
- Wolf/Hound (CUNA,
- God Lugh (LUG,
- Battle (CATTU,
- Heaven/Cow (ERC,
- one who is blind (DALAGNI,
- one with an elegant eye (DERCMASOC,
- No persons described
- Father/Son (MAQI,
- Tribe (MUOI,
- Descendant (AVI,
- Follower (CELI,
- name (ANM,
- here is (KOI,

TEI EPIDOC Example from Ogham in 3D

```
<TEI xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0">
  <teiHeader>
    <fileDesc>
      <titleStmt>
        <title>CIIC 178. Coumeenole</title>
        <editor>
          <persName>Nora White</persName>
          <roleName>Principal Investigator</roleName>
          <orgName>Dublin Institute for Advanced Studies</orgName>
        </editor>
        <respStmt>
          <resp>3D laser scanned using Artec Eva scanner on 20/6/2013 and later processed using Geomagic software</resp>
          <name>Gary Devlin</name>
          <orgName>Discovery Programme</orgName>
        </respStmt>
      </titleStmt>
      <publicationStmt>
        <distributor>Dublin Institute for Advanced Studies</distributor>
        <pubPlace>Dublin</pubPlace>
        <availability>
          <licence target="http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/3.0/ie/deed.en_US">
            <p>This work is licensed under the Creative Commons licence Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 3.0 Ireland</p>
            <p>Copyright (c) 2013 by the School of Celtic Studies</p>
            <ref>http://www.celt.dias.ie</ref></p>
            <p>All reuse or distribution of this work must contain somewhere a reference to <ref>http://ogham.celt.dias.ie/</ref></p>
          </licence>
        </availability>
      </publicationStmt>
    </fileDesc>
  </teiHeader>
  <text>
    <p><b>E22 Human-Made Object</b></p>
    <p><b>P1 is identified by</b></p>
    <p><b>L1 digitized</b></p>
    <p><b>D9 Data Object</b></p>
  </text>
</TEI>
```


CIIC 178. Coumeenole North, Co. Kerry

via <https://ogham.celt.dias.ie/stone.php?lang=en&site=Coumeenole&stone=178>. Coumeenole&stoneinfo=epidoc_view

```
<div type="description" n="monument">
  <head>Monument</head>
  <p>
    <rs type="material"/>Grit (<ref type="bibliog" target="#MAC1945"
      ><bibl><author>Macalister</author>
        <date when="1945">1945</date>, <biblScope type="pp"
          >163</biblScope></bibl></ref>), <rs type="dimensions">
        <measure unit="metre" type="length" rend="height">2.00</measure>m x
        <measure unit="metre" type="length" rend="width">0.45</measure>m x
        <measure unit="metre" type="length" rend="depth">0.30</measure>m
      <lb/> .</rs>
    </p>
</div>
```

P40 observed dimension

E16 Measurement

```
<div type="edition" xml:lang="ga">
  <head xml:lang="en">Transliteration</head>
  <ab>
    <persName><w lemma="ERC">ERC</w></persName>
    <w lemma="MAQI" type="formula">MAQI</w>
    <persName><w lemma="MAQI-ERCIAS">MAQI-ERCIA<unclear>S</unclear></w></persName>
    <w lemma="MUCOI?" type="formula"><unclear>MU</unclear></w>
    <persName><w lemma="DOVINIAS"
      >DOVI<unclear>N</unclear>I<unclear>A</unclear></w></persName>
    </ab>
  </div>
<div type="translation" xml:lang="en">
  <head>Translation</head>
  <ab><q>of Erc son of Mac-Erce descendant? of Duibne</q></ab>
</div>
```

P56 bears feature

E25 Human-Made Feature

```
<div type="history" n="locations">
  <head>Locations</head>
  <div type="history" n="locations">
    <head>Found</head>
    <p>
      <rs type="found">lying prostrate on the summit of the promontory called Dunmore Head (<ref type="bibliog"
        target="#MAC1945"><bibl><author>Macalister</author>
          <date when="1945">1945</date>, <biblScope type="pp"
            >170</biblScope></bibl></ref>) in the townland of <placeName
              type="townland">Coumeenole</placeName> and barony of <placeName
                type="barony">Corkaguiney</placeName>. (GPS coordinates <geo>-10.473639, 52.110137</geo>)</rs>
      </p>
    </div>
  </div>
  <div type="history" n="locations">
    <head>Original</head>
    <p>
      <rs type="origlocation">Find location possibly original site</rs>
    </p>
  </div>
  <div type="history" n="locations">
    <head>Last Recorded</head>
    <p>
      <rs type="lastlocation">At or close to find site on Dún Mór promontory fort <ref
        target="http://webgis.archaeology.ie/HistoricEnvironment/?SMRS=KE052-059002-"
          >National Monuments Service Historic Environment viewer on
            www.archaeology.ie</ref>. </rs>
    </p>
  </div>
  <div type="history" n="record">
    <head>History of Recording</head>
    <p><q>discovered by the Cork antiquaries Windele, Abell, and Horgan, in 1838; and was re-erected in the
      following year by a local priest, Rev. J. Casey</q> <ref type="bibliog" target="#MAC1945"
        ><bibl><author>Macalister</author>
          <date when="1945">1945</date>, <biblScope type="pp"
            >170</biblScope></bibl></ref>.</p>
  </div>
```

E53 Place

P53 has former or current location

CIIC 178. Coumeenole North, Co. Kerry

Wie geht man mit Annotationen im 3D-Raum um?

⇒ NFDI4Objects TWG: 3D-Annotation von Meshes mit dem Web Annotation Data Model

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Thiery, Florian, Thiery Homburg, Anne-Karoline Distel, and Peter Thiery. 2024. '3D Und FDM: Beispiele Für Semantische 3D-Annotation Und -Modellierung Im Datenqualifizierungsprozess in Konsortien Der Nationalen Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI)'. In Photogrammetrie – Laserscanning – Optische 3D-Messtechnik. Beiträge Der Oldenburger 3D-Tage und des BIMtages 2024., edited by Thomas Luhmann and Till Sieberth, 84–93. Berlin: Wichmann Verlag.

3D-Annotationen Beispiel

Objekt RGZM, Foto: Lübke & Wiedemann, Leonberg

Vanessa Liebler für das i3mainz, CC BY SA 4.0

336 Objekte: erhaltene Objekte, Rekonstruktionen, Fragmente Schalen, Teller, Öllampen, Kannen Fertigungsobjekte für die Appliken (Model, Stempel)

African Red Slip Ware (ARS) Objekte des LEIZA, FAIRifiziert im ARS3D-Projekt (BMBF)

Florian Thieri, CC BY 4.0

African Red Slip Ware digital (ARS3D) Ontologie

- **Main Classes**

- ars:ARS_Object/Manufacturing_Object (**E22** Man-Made Object)
- ars:FeatureType_Applique/FeatureType_Mould/FeatureTypeStamp (**E25** Man-Made Feature)
- ars:Statement (**I1** Argumentation, via *CRM_{inf}*)
- sci_S4:Observation (**S4** Observation, via *CRM_{sci}*)
- inf:I1_Argumentation (**I1** Argumentation, via *CRM_{inf}*)
- ars:Interpretation/Human_Interpretation (**E55** Type)

- **Main Properties**

- crm:P56 (**P56** bears feature) [**O**→**F**]
- crm:P62 (**P62** depicts) [**F**→**Obs**]
- sci:O8 (**O8** observed, via *CRM_{sci}*) [**Obs**→**Obs**]
- crm:P67 (**P67** refers to) [**A**→**Obs**]
- ars:is_stated_by (= **P67** refers to) [**O/F/Obs**→**S**]

CRM_{sci}
Scientific observation
model

CRM_{inf}
Argumentation model

ARS3D in CIDOC CRM

Hercules killing the lion
Applique (positive)
Statement: Armstrong 8.107
Hercules
Statement: Löwenstein Hercules X
lion
man

Powered by 3DHOPE

CC BY-SA 4.0 | Römisch-Germanisches Zentralmuseum Leibniz-Forschungsinstitut für Archäologie | i3mainz - Institut für Raumbezogene Informations- und Messtechnik
ARS3D African Red Slip Ware digital is funded by BMBF | Impressum | Datenschutz

Features

Hercules killing the lion

»Applique (positive)« related to 0 Feature(s) and described with 5 observations(s)

Statement > Armstrong 8.107

Hercules > beardless, holding, killing, looking to the left, muscular, naked

Statement > Löwenstein Hercules X

lion > held by figure left

man > beardless, holding, killing, looking to the left, muscular, naked

bow and arrow

»Applique (positive)« related to 0 Feature(s) and described with 3 observations(s)

Statement > Armstrong 1.44

arrow

bow

Interpretations

Hercules

i arguments

Supportive Argument > Armstrong 8.107 (Statement)

Supportive Argument > Löwenstein Hercules XI (Statement)

Main Argument > arrow (Observation)

Main Argument > man (Observation)

Main Argument > bow (Observation)

Main Argument > club (Observation)

Hercules' fight with the Nemean lion

i arguments

Supportive Argument > Löwenstein Hercules im Kampf gegen den Löwen (Statement)

Main Argument > man (Observation)

Main Argument > arrow (Observation)

Main Argument > lion (Observation)

Main Argument > bow (Observation)

Main Argument > club (Observation)

3D-Annotationen speichern?

```

RDF4J.createFeature = (object, uuid, label, process, processid, geom, type, callback) => {
  console.log(object, uuid, label, process, geom, type);
  let THIS_UPDATE = "INSERT DATA { ";
  // feature data
  THIS_UPDATE += "ars3df:" + uuid + " " + "rdf:type" + " " + "crm:E25_Man-Made_Feature ." ;
  THIS_UPDATE += "ars3df:" + uuid + " " + "rdf:type" + " " + "dig:D9_Data_Object ." ;
  THIS_UPDATE += "ars3df:" + uuid + " " + "rdfs:label" + " " + "'" + label + "'@en" + " ." ;
  THIS_UPDATE += "ars3df:" + uuid + " " + "crm:P2_has_type " + type + " ." ;
  geom = JSON.stringify(geom);
  geom = geom.replace(/\"/g, "\\");
  THIS_UPDATE += "ars3df:" + uuid + " " + "ars:hasGeometricalExtent" + " " + "\"" + geom + "\"" + " ." ;
  THIS_UPDATE += "ars3df:" + uuid + " " + "dig:L31_has_starting_date-time" + " " + "'" + processid + "'" + " ." ;
  THIS_UPDATE += "ars3df:" + uuid + " " + "dig:L30_has_operator" + " " + "'" + CURRENT_OPERATOR + "'" + " ." ;
  // process data
  THIS_UPDATE += "ars3dgp:" + processid + " " + "rdf:type" + " " + "dig:D10_Software_Execution" + " ." ;
  THIS_UPDATE += "ars3dgp:" + processid + " " + "dig:L10_had_input" + " " + "ars3df:" + uuid + " ." ;
  THIS_UPDATE += "ars3dgp:" + processid + " " + "dig:L31_has_starting_date-time" + " " + "'" + processid + "'" + " ." ;
  THIS_UPDATE += "ars3dgp:" + processid + " " + "ars:hasProcessState" + " " + "'" + process + "'" + " ." ;
  // object connection
  THIS_UPDATE += " " + object + " " + "crm:P56_bears_feature" + " " + "ars3df:" + uuid + " ." ;
  THIS_UPDATE += " }";
}

```

JavaScript-Code ⇒ createFeature()

```

RDF4J.createObservation = (OBSERVATIONTYPE, observationName, ACTIVITIES, CONDITIONS, THISFEATURE, callback) => {
  console.log(OBSERVATIONTYPE, observationName, ACTIVITIES, CONDITIONS, THISFEATURE);
  let obsID = UUID.getUUIDv4();
  let obsItemID = UUID.getUUIDv4();
  let d = new Date();
  let n = d.getTime();
  let THIS_UPDATE = "INSERT DATA { ";
  // feature data
  THIS_UPDATE += "ars3dobs:" + obsID + " " + "rdf:type" + " " + "sci:S4_Observation . ";
  THIS_UPDATE += "ars3dobs:" + obsID + " " + "rdf:type" + " " + "dig:D10_Software_Execution" + ". ";
  THIS_UPDATE += "ars3dobs:" + obsID + " " + "rdfs:label" + " " + "'" + observationName + "'@en" + ". ";
  THIS_UPDATE += "ars3dobs:" + obsID + " " + "dig:L31_has_starting_date-time" + " " + "'" + n + "'" + ". ";
  THIS_UPDATE += "ars3dobs:" + obsID + " " + "dig:L30_has_operator" + " " + "'" + CURRENT_OPERATOR + "'" + ". ";
  THIS_UPDATE += "ars3dobs:" + obsID + " " + "sci:08_observed" + " " + "ars3dobs:" + obsItemID + ". ";
  THIS_UPDATE += "ars3dobs:" + obsItemID + " " + "rdf:type" + " " + "sci:S4_Observation . ";
  THIS_UPDATE += "ars3dobs:" + obsItemID + " " + "crm:P2:has_type" + " " + OBSERVATIONTYPE + ". ";
  for (i in ACTIVITIES) {
    THIS_UPDATE += "ars3dobs:" + obsItemID + " " + "sci:08_observed" + " " + ACTIVITIES[i].uri + ". ";
  }
  for (i in CONDITIONS) {
    THIS_UPDATE += "ars3dobs:" + obsItemID + " " + "sci:08_observed" + " " + CONDITIONS[i].uri + ". ";
  }
  // feature connection
  THIS_UPDATE += THISFEATURE + " " + "crm:P62_depicts" + " " + "ars3dobs:" + obsID + ". ";
  THIS_UPDATE += " }";
}

```

JavaScript-Code ⇒ createObservation()

E25 als D9 Digital Object

```
ars3df:ed904143-b4c3-4bd3-81dc-2e8892a028ad a crm:E25_Man-Made_Feature .  
ars3df:ed904143-b4c3-4bd3-81dc-2e8892a028ad a dig:D9_Data_Object .  
ars3df:ed904143-b4c3-4bd3-81dc-2e8892a028ad rdfs:label "Hercules killing the lion"@en .  
ars3df:ed904143-b4c3-4bd3-81dc-2e8892a028ad crm:P2_has_type arsono:FeatureType_Applique .  
ars3df:ed904143-b4c3-4bd3-81dc-2e8892a028ad dig:L31_has_starting_date-time "1592637393887" .  
ars3df:ed904143-b4c3-4bd3-81dc-2e8892a028ad dig:L30_has_operator "Samantha Beck" .
```

Annotation als Prozess

```
ars3dp:1592637393887 a dig:D10_Software_Execution .  
ars3dp:1592637393887 dig:L10_had_input ars3df:ed904143-b4c3-4bd3-81dc-2e8892a028ad .  
ars3dp:1592637393887 dig:L31_has_starting_date-time "1592637393887" .  
ars3dp:1592637393887 arsono:hasProcessState> "step1" .
```

3D-Annotation in CIDOC CRM

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

via <https://romanopendata.eu/#/>

Courtesy of Verulamium Museum Kate Warren, via archaeologydataservice.ac.uk

Amphib/Type/Title	Area/Title	Findings/Year/Title	Simplified/Transcription
Amphib	Amphib	1911/1911	AMPHIB
Amphib	Amphib	1911/1911	AMPHIB
Amphib	Amphib	1911/1911	AMPHIB
Amphib	Amphib	1911/1911	AMPHIB
Amphib	Amphib	1911/1911	AMPHIB
Amphib	Amphib	1911/1911	AMPHIB
Amphib	Amphib	1911/1911	AMPHIB
Amphib	Amphib	1911/1911	AMPHIB
Amphib	Amphib	1911/1911	AMPHIB
Amphib	Amphib	1911/1911	AMPHIB

Epigraphies & Amphoras from the CEIPAC database

via <https://romanopendata.eu/sparql/doc/index.html>

Roman Open Data Ontology

- **Main Classes**

- rod:InformationCarrier (E22 Human-Made Object)
- rod:Inscription (E25 Human-Made Feature / TX1 Written Text, via CRMtex)
- rod:LinguisticObject (E25 Human-Made Feature / TX7 Written Text Segment, via CRMtex)
- rod:Person (E39 Actor)
- rod:TemporalEntity (E2 Temporal Entity)
- rod:AmphoraType (E55 Type)
- rod:Image (D9 Data Object, via CRMdig)
- rod:BibliographicResource (E31 Document)
- rod:Place (E53 Place)

CRMdig
Model for provenance
metadata

CRMtex
Textual Entities Model

- **Main Properties**

- rod:carries (P56 bears feature) [IC→In]
- rod:isAbout (P62 depicts) [In→Pe]
- rod:isTranscribedBy (TXP4 has segment, via CRMtex) [In→LO]
- rod:hasProductionDate (P164 is temporally specified by) [IC→TE]
- rod:isDocumentedBy (P67 refers to) [IC→BR]
- rod:isDocumentedBy (L60i is documented by, via CRMdig) [IC→I]
- rod:hasAmphoraType (P2 has type) [IC→AT]
- rod:hasFindingPlace (P53 has former or current location) [IC→P]
- rod:fallsWithin (P89 falls within) [P→P]

Nur eine
hypothetische
CRM-Modellierung!

CEIPAC Amphoras in CIDOC CRM

Classes

[Authenticity](#), [CoinWear](#), [Collection](#), [Context](#), [Controlmark](#), [Corrosion](#), [Countermark](#), [Denomination](#), [DepositionType](#), [DieWear](#), [DiscoveryType](#), [Ethnic](#), [FieldOfNumismatics](#), [Find](#), [Hoard](#), [Manufacture](#), [Material](#), [Mint](#), [Mintmark](#), [Monogram](#), [NumismaticObject](#), [NumismaticTerm](#), [ObjectType](#), [Peculiarity](#), [PeculiarityOfProduction](#), [ReferenceWork](#), [Region](#), [SecondaryTreatment](#), [Shape](#), [StratigraphicUnit](#), [TypeSeries](#), [TypeSeriesItem](#), [Wear](#), [WeightStandard](#)

Object Properties

[hasAppearance](#), [hasAuthenticity](#), [hasAuthority](#), [hasAxis](#), [hasBearsDate](#), [hasCollection](#), [hasContemporaryName](#), [hasContext](#), [hasControlmark](#), [hasCorrosion](#), [hasCountermark](#), [hasDate](#), [hasDenomination](#), [hasDepth](#), [hasDiameter](#), [hasDie](#), [hasEdge](#), [hasEndDate](#), [hasFace](#), [hasFieldOfNumismatics](#), [hasFindSpot](#), [hasHeight](#), [hasIconography](#), [hasIssuer](#), [hasLegend](#), [hasManufacture](#), [hasMaterial](#), [hasMaxDepth](#), [hasMaxDiameter](#), [hasMaxHeight](#), [hasMaxWidth](#), [hasMinDepth](#), [hasMinDiameter](#), [hasMinHeight](#), [hasMinWidth](#), [hasMint](#), [hasMintmark](#), [hasNumismaticObject](#), [hasObjectType](#), [hasObverse](#), [hasPeculiarity](#), [hasPeculiarityOfProduction](#), [hasPortrait](#), [hasProductionDate](#), [hasProductionObject](#), [hasReferenceWork](#), [hasReverse](#), [hasScholarlyName](#), [hasSecondaryTreatment](#), [hasShape](#), [hasStartDate](#), [hasStatedAuthority](#), [hasTypeSeriesItem](#), [hasWear](#), [hasWeight](#), [hasWeightStandard](#), [hasWidth](#), [isAbove](#), [isBelow](#), [isEqual](#), [representsObjectType](#), [reproductionOf](#)

nomisma.org Ontology

E22 Human-Made Object

NumismaticObject

BY ZEENA - PUBLISHED 01/05/2022 - UPDATED 23/11/2022

IRI: <http://nomisma.org/ontology#NumismaticObject>

Note: Objects considered to be within the numismatic domain.

Examples: Coins, Tokens, Banknotes etc.

Use case: a.

RDF/XML:

```
<rdf:Description rdf:about="Coin_1">
  <rdf:type rdf:resource="nmo:NumismaticObject"/>
</rdf:Description>
```

Use case: b.

Find

BY ZEENA - PUBLISHED 02/05/2022 - UPDATED 12/01/2023

IRI: <http://nomisma.org/ontology#Find>

has Superclasses: [Context](#)

has Subclasses: [Hoard](#)

Note: A numismatic object or group of numismatic objects that was lost or deposited, whether intentionally or unintentionally, in previous times, and subsequently recovered. The recovery takes place independently of any intention of retrieval associated with the original deposition. Examples: Group of coins found, contains of "content", context of deposition "loss".

Use case:

E22 Human-Made Object ???

Hoard

BY ZEENA - PUBLISHED 02/05/2022 - UPDATED 12/01/2023

IRI: <http://nomisma.org/ontology#Hoard>

has Superclasses: [Find](#)

Class instances: [nm:olivers_orchard_hoards](#), [nm:normanby_hoard](#), [nm:liria_hoard](#), [nm:brauweiler_hoard](#)

Note: A group of numismatic objects: a store of wealth concealed with intent of recovery but which, for reasons not usually known to us, was not recovered until modern times.

Examples: Hoard was found in year_, in location_, and contains of table of content_.

Use case: a.

nomisma.org classes

Mint

E53 Place

BY ZEENA · PUBLISHED 01/05/2022 · UPDATED 23/11/2022

IRI: <http://nomisma.org/ontology#Mint>

Class instances: [nm:asculum](#), [nm:comama](#), [nm:cennatis](#), [nm:argos_argolis](#), ...

Object property: [nmo:hasMint](#)

Note: Generic term for a place of manufacture of a numismatic object or for the issuing city.

Use case: a.

Material

E57 Material

BY ZEENA · PUBLISHED 02/05/2022 · UPDATED 23/11/2022

IRI: <http://nomisma.org/ontology#Material>

Class instances: [nm:ar](#), [nm:ae](#), [nm:av](#), [nm:glass](#), [nm:clay](#), ...

Object property: [nmo:hasMaterial](#)

Note: The physical material from which an object is made.

Examples: Gold, Silver, Bronze. Coin was made from material_x, which is composed of (20%τ, 15%μ, 65%φ) (if material is not defined among the Nomisma-IDs for Material).

Use case: a.

RDF/XML:

```
<rdf:Description rdf:about="Coin_1">
  <nmo:hasMaterial rdf:resource="nm:av"/>
</rdf:Description>
```

Use case: b.

nomisma.org classes

hasFindspot P53 has former or current location

BY ZEENA · PUBLISHED 30/04/2022 · UPDATED 12/01/2023

IRI: <http://nomisma.org/ontology#hasFindspot>

Note: Describes the location of the discovery of an object, whether by accident or in archaeological excavation.

Use case:

hasIssuer P94 has created ???

BY ZEENA · PUBLISHED 29/04/2022 · UPDATED 12/01/2023

IRI: <http://nomisma.org/ontology#hasIssuer>

Related concepts: [Person](#)

Note: Identifies the person administratively responsible for the issue of a numismatic object, generally named in some capacity on the object.

Example: Coin minted in Maroneia, issued by Metrodotos.

Use case:

nomisma.org properties

hasMint P53 has former or current location ???

BY ZEENA · PUBLISHED 29/04/2022 · UPDATED 23/11/2022

IRI: <http://nomisma.org/ontology#hasMint>

Related classes: [nmo:Mint](#)

Note: Identifies the place of manufacture or issue of a numismatic object.

Examples: Rome, comama, etc., Coin_1 minted in comama is certain, Coin_x minted either in comama or in cretopolis, is uncertain (example of two uncertainty modeling options).

Use case: a.

nomisma.org properties

hasIconography **P56 bears feature**

BY ZEENA - PUBLISHED 29/04/2022 - UPDATED 12/01/2023

IRI: <http://nomisma.org/ontology#hasIconography>

has Superproperties: [hasAppearance](#)

has Subproperties: [hasCountermark](#) , [hasPortrait](#)

Related concepts: [Person](#), [Deity](#)

Note: Describes an iconography placed on a numismatic object.

Examples: Iconography of (a person, a deity, an animal, a symbol, an object, etc.), as the main figure or as a Countermark.

Use case: a.

hasLegend **P56 bears feature**

BY ZEENA - PUBLISHED 29/04/2022 - UPDATED 12/01/2023

IRI: <http://nomisma.org/ontology#hasLegend>

has Superproperties: [hasAppearance](#)

Note: Describes the inscription or printing placed on a numismatic object as part of the production process.

Examples: Coin minted in Rome, showing portrait of Titus and legend on the obverse, and showing figure of the goddess Fortuna and a legend on the reverse.

Use case: a.

nomisma.org properties

Use Cases

CIDOC CRM

... aus Citizen-Science Systemen

Use Cases

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Article

Practices of Linked Open Data in Archaeology and Their Realisation in Wikidata

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Abstract

In this paper, we introduce Linked Open Data (LOD) in the archaeological domain as a means to connect dispersed data sources and enable cross-querying. The technology behind the design principles and how LOD can be created and published is described to enable less-familiar researchers to understand the presented benefits and drawbacks of LOD. Wikidata is introduced as an open knowledge hub for the creation and dissemination of LOD. Different actors within archaeology have implemented LOD, and we present which challenges have been and are being addressed. A selection of projects showcases how Wikidata is being used by archaeologists to enrich and open their databases to the general public. With this paper, we aim to encourage the creation and re-use of LOD in archaeology, as we believe it offers an improvement on current data publishing practices.

Keywords: linked open data; Wikidata; archaeology

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Linked Data & Wikidata in archaeology

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<https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q465338>

<https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q249707>

<https://www.wikidata.org/entity/P189>

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Linked Data in Wikidata: An example

Grafiken: Martina Trognitz, CC BY 4.0, via 10.3390/digital2030019

Linked Data in Wikidata: An example

❖ **Items**

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Item [Discussion](#)

Phaistos disc (Q465338)

inscribed tablet found in Crete with undeciphered spiral scriptures

edit

Phaistos Disk | Phaestos Disc

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Phaistos disc	inscribed tablet found in Crete with undeciphered spiral scriptures	Phaistos Disk Phaestos Disc
German	Diskos von Phaistos	Tonscheibe aus der Bronzezeit	Diskos von Festós Diskos von Phaistós Phaistos Phaistos-Scheibe Diskos von Festos
Italian	disco di Festo	disco di terracotta rinvenuto nell'isola di Creta	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

instance of	clay tablet
	► 1 reference
	archaeological artifact
	▼ 0 references
	+ add reference
	+ add value

via <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q465338>

Phaistos Disc (Q465338)

inception	<div> <p>17. century BCE edit</p> <p>1 reference</p> </div>
	<div> <p>1850 BCE edit</p> <p>earliest date 1850 BCE</p> <p>latest date 1600 BCE</p> <p>sourcing circumstances circa</p> <p>1 reference</p> </div>
	<div> <p>1400 BCE edit</p> <p>latest date 1301 BCE</p> <p>sourcing circumstances after</p> <p>1 reference</p> </div>
	<div> <p>1700 BCE edit</p> <p>earliest date 1700 BCE</p> <p>latest date 1100 BCE</p> <p>sourcing circumstances circa</p> <p>reason for preferred rank preferred determination method</p> <p>1 reference</p> <p>author Louis Godart</p> <p>page(s) 206</p> <p>stated in Le pouvoir de l'écrit</p> <p>+ add reference</p> </div>
	<div> <p>1400 BCE edit</p> <p>earliest date 1400 BCE</p> <p>latest date 1340 BCE</p> <p>sourcing circumstances circa</p> <p>1 reference</p> <p>+ add value</p> </div>

country	<div> <p>Greece edit</p> <p>0 references + add reference</p> </div>
	<div> <p>Ancient Crete edit</p> <p>0 references + add reference</p> </div>
	<div> <p>Minoan civilization edit</p> <p>0 references + add reference</p> <p>+ add value</p> </div>
located in the administrative territorial entity	<div> <p>Heraklion Prefecture edit</p> <p>0 references + add reference</p> <p>+ add value</p> </div>
location	<div> <p>Heraklion Archaeological Museum edit</p> <p>1 reference + add value</p> </div>
coordinate location	<div> <p>35°3'6.05"N, 24°48'53.60"E</p> <p>1 reference</p> <p>imported from Wikimedia project Catalan Wikipedia</p> <p>+ add reference</p> <p>+ add value</p> </div>

via <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q465338>

Phaistos Disc (Q465338)

query.wikidata.org

Wikidata SPARQL Query: Archäologische Artefakte

Wikidata Archäologische Artefakte (?)

Wikidata Archäologische Artefakte (?)

Wikidata Archäologische Artefakte (?)

Item [Discussion](#)

Boundary stone with eagle (Q17445038)

monument in Vaals, Netherlands [edit](#)

[In more languages](#)

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Boundary stone with eagle	monument in Vaals, Netherlands	
German	Adlerstein Grenzstein (Aachen)	Vaals, Netherlands	Adlerstein am Vaalser Berg („Sc...
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

[All entered languages](#)

Statements

instance of	 boundary marker edit
	→ 0 references + add reference
 monolith	edit
	→ 0 references + add reference
 archaeological artifact	edit
	→ 0 references + add reference
+ add value	

image	 edit
	<p>Vaals-Grenssteen achter Wilhelmintoren (1).JPG</p> <p>3,000 × 4,000, 4.11 MB</p> <p>point in time 22 November 2010</p>

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Aachener Adler-Grenzstein (Q17445038)

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Project page Discussion

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Wikidata:WikiProject OghamStones

- Wikidata Entry: WikiProject OghamStones (Q128491028) supported by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network (Q73501910)
- Commons Category: Category:Ogham stones?

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Statements to model an Ogham Stone in an exhibition [edit]

Property	Example	description
Statements		
instance of (P171)	ogham stone (Q2016147) Ogham Stone Semantic Concept (Q109852843) archaeological artifact (Q227858)	defines it as an Ogham Stone, archaeological artefact and Ogham Stone Semantic Concept
part of (P1981)	WikiProject OghamStones (Q128491028) Ogham Stone Semantic Concept (Q109852843)	part of WikiProjects and a semantic concept
image (P18)	divers	Wikimedia Commons image, if multiple add pref. rank (optional)
country (P171)	divers	country, e.g. Ireland (Q27)
located in the administrative territorial entity (P131)	divers	county, e.g. County Cork (Q162478)
location (P1278)	divers	museum + exhibition, e.g. University College Cork (Q1514188) + UCC Stone Corridor (Q121592048)
coordinate location (P1825)	WGS84	using qualifier location (P1278) ex situ (Q1363333), sourcing circumstances (P1485) on-site survey (Q123085429), determination method (P1450) on-site survey (Q123085429), subject has role (P12985) exhibition (Q46468), stated in (P1248) OpenStreetMap (Q268), reference OpenStreetMap node ID (P11850), add pref. rank
creator (P170)	Ogham Person Concept (Q110891921)	Ogham Person as creator (only needed if non-free artwork image URL (P1850) is used)
collection (P195)	divers	collection, e.g. Stone Corridor University College Cork (Q26379477)
inventory number (P1217)	divers	Inventory number of the collection, set a pref. rank
location of discovery (P180)	divers	ogham site, e.g. Barmahaurin (Ogham Site) (Q6937412)
external data available at URL (P1325)	URL	ref. to 3D-model in Sketchfab, using qualifier object of statement has role (P13631) 3D model (Q268633), publisher (P1123), published in (P1433), copyright license (P1275), add pref. rank
inscription (P1584)	latin	inscription, e.g. C[AR]RTTACC MMAQI MOIU CAGG (Latin)
state of conservation (P1518)	divers	status, e.g. partially destroyed (Q2639180) (optional)
non-free artwork image URL (P1850)	divers	external image (optional), using qualifier copyright license (P1275), publisher (P1123), object of statement has role (P13631)
partially coincident with (P1382)	divers	other concepts, e.g., BARHA/1 (Ogham Stone Concept by CISP) (Q10897539), CMC 103 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister) (Q6937780)
Identifiers		
OpenStreetMap node ID (P11862)	divers	Open Street Map Node

Wikidata WikiProject OghamStones

Statements to model an Ogham Stone in the wild [edit]

Property	Example	description
instance of (P31)	ogham stone (Q2018147) Ogham Stone Semantic Concept (Q108802843) archaeological artifact (Q220669)	defines it as an Ogham Stone, archaeological artefact and Ogham Stone Semantic Concept
part of (P381)	WikiProject OghamStones (Q126491028) Ogham Stone Semantic Concept (Q108802843)	part of WikiProjects and a semantic concept
image (P18)	divers	Wikimedia Commons image, if multiple add <i>pref. rank</i> (optional)
non-free artwork image URL (P6500)	divers	external image (optional), using qualifier <i>copyright license</i> (P275), <i>publisher</i> (P123), <i>object of statement has role</i> (P3831)
country (P17)	divers	country, e.g. Ireland (Q27)
located in the administrative territorial entity (P131)	divers	county, e.g. County Cork (Q182475)
location (P276)	divers	location in the wild
coordinate location (P825)	WGS84	using qualifier <i>location</i> (P276) <i>ex situ</i> (Q1383330), <i>sourcing circumstances</i> (P1480) <i>on-site survey</i> (Q120965429), <i>determination method</i> (P459) <i>on-site survey</i> (Q120965429), <i>subject has role</i> (P2868) <i>exhibition</i> (Q464980), <i>stated in</i> (P248) <i>OpenStreetMap</i> (Q936); reference <i>OpenStreetMap node ID</i> (P11893), add <i>pref. rank</i>
collection (P195)	divers	collection (optional)
inscription (P1884)	latin	inscription, e.g. C[A]RRTTACC MMAQI MO/U CAGG (Latin)
state of conservation (P5816)	divers	status, e.g. <i>partially destroyed</i> (Q80539180) (optional)
partially coincident with (P1382)	divers	other concepts, e.g., BARHA/1 (Ogham Stone Concept by CISP) (Q108875359), CIIC 103 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister) (Q69377860)
OpenStreetMap node ID (P11893)	divers	Open Street Map Node
Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID (P4057)	divers	SMR ID (optional)

Wikidata WikiProject OghamStones

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Ogham Stone Coumeenole North / Dunmore Head, Co. Kerry (Q126503090)

Ogham Stone, Co. Kerry
Coumeenole Stone edit

▼ In more languages
Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Ogham Stone Coumeenole North / Dunmore Head, Co. Kerry	Ogham Stone, Co. Kerry	Coumeenole Stone
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

instance of	ogham stone edit
	▼ 0 references
	+ add reference
Ogham Stone Semantic Concept edit	
	▼ 0 references
	+ add reference
archaeological artifact edit	
	▼ 0 references
	+ add reference
+ add value	

Ogham Stone at Dunmore Head in Wikidata

	Property	Example	
	instance of (P31)	ogham stone (Q2016147) Ogham Stone Semantic Concept (Q106602643) archaeological artifact (Q220659)	<u>E22</u> Human-Made Object
	part of (P361)	WikiProject OghamStones (Q126491026) Ogham Stone Semantic Concept (Q106602643)	
<u>L60i</u> is documented by	image (P18)	divers	<u>D9</u> Data Object
	non-free artwork image URL (P6500)	divers	
	country (P17)	divers	
<u>P53</u> has former or current location	located in the administrative territorial entity (P131)	divers	<u>E53</u> Place
	location (P276)	divers	
	coordinate location (P625)	WGS84	
	collection (P195)	divers	
<u>P56</u> bears feature	inscription (P1684)	latin	<u>E25</u> Human-Made Feature
	state of conservation (P5816)	divers	
	partially coincident with (P1382)	divers	
	OpenStreetMap node ID (P11693)	divers	
	Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID (P4057)	divers	

Ogham Stone (Wikidata) in CIDOC CRM

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Wikidata:WikiProject HolyWells

Wikidata Entry: WikiProject HolyWells (Q2284348) supported by the Research Squiral Engineers Network (Q2301571)

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- 1.7 External projects using the data

Holy Wells in Ireland [edit]

This project was begun using the holy wells of County Kilkenny, but can be used for other counties, adjusting the sources etc.

- [Wikipedia Category:Holy wells in County Kilkenny?](#)
- [Wikimedia Category:Holy wells in County Kilkenny?](#)

Statements to model a holy well in Ireland [edit]

Use English and Irish labels in the header, where known.

Property	Example/ further qualifiers	Explanation
instance of (P31)	Holy Well Semantic Concept (Q2284332)	always use this: defines it as a holy well, no matter whether there is still veneration happening or not.
	holy well (Q1317047)	
instance of (P31)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • state of use (P5817) "in use" for holy wells where veneration is still happening or "abandoned", where that is the case • state of conservation (P5816): preserved (Q26579187) / in danger (Q26583051) / demolished or destroyed (Q2658151) • reference URL (P1624) 6 inch First Edition Ordnance Survey map of Ireland (Q1282610) and/or Historic Environment Viewer (Ireland) (Q12588154) or any of the ones under described by source (P1343), where it is described as a holy well and not merely a "Spring" or "Well" 	holy wells on the old OS maps are written in Gothic letters, so even if the name does not suggest association with a saint or cure, it was considered holy at the time of the survey
instance of (P31)	religious site (Q11582895)	only where veneration is still happening, i.e. annual patterns or people regularly visiting the well for private prayers or to retrieve the holy water
instance of (P31)	water source (Q11713494) spring (Q124174) water well (Q40437) pumping station (Q44613)	Depending what the sources describe them as, add references to your selection. This can have changed over time from 6 inch First Edition Ordnance Survey map of Ireland (Q1282610) to now.
named after (P138)	Brigit of Kildare (Q2619)	saint representing patron saint or
	eye (Q1284)	body part representing cure for ailment or
feast day (P194)	state of use (P5817)	other characteristic it is named after
country (P17)	Ireland (Q27)	pattern day(s), if it is still celebrated, use state of use (P5817) "in use", if no longer celebrated, use "abandoned".
	---	---
located in the administrative territorial entity (P131)	County Kilkenny (Q181221) • Balleen (Q2653357)	County + civil parish
diocese (P198)	Roman Catholic Diocese of Ossory (Q87367)	Roman Catholic diocese in which the holy well is located
coordinate location (P152)		coordinate location derived from OpenStreetMap or Historic Environment Viewer
street address (P157)		add reference URL (P1624) or stated in (P1348)
		use, when the only location given is a field name or similar
described by source (P1343)	O'Kelly, The Place-Names of County Kilkenny (Q12834801) Historic Environment Viewer (Ireland) (Q12588154) The Schools' Collection (Q12835245) Canon W. Carrigan: The History and Antiquities of the Diocese of Ossory (Q1284042) with its volumes 6 inch First Edition Ordnance Survey map of Ireland (Q1282610)	add page(s) (P1304) or reference URL (P1624)
image (P18)		Wikimedia link to image
video (P14)		Wikimedia link to video
Commons category (P53)	Category:Tobarbrida, Galain?	
YouTube video ID (P1981)		YouTube video link
external data available at URL (P152)	diverse	use for Skelchfab (full) links or similar
mouth of the watercourse (P403)		Which water course does it feed into?
collection (P170)	Pádraig Ó Dálaigh: The holy wells of County Kilkenny II (Q12815543)	if the holy well is described in a survey, you can add the survey under the Property of "Collection". This is necessary for the next Property of Inventory number (P151)
inventory number (P151)		Add the number or reference in the collection(s) and add the appropriate collection as a qualifier.
Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID (P460)	KK008-133---	plus reference URL (P1624)
OpenStreetMap node ID (P11893)	6153432366	if the SMR no. has been decommissioned, i.e. you find the old somewhere in the Atlantic Ocean, add the qualifier state of use "abandoned".
illustrator (P110)	Bruce D Mssitar	OpenStreetMap Node ID or way ID
		if there is a drawing or photograph (or more) available in a book with a named photographer, use this in addition to "described by source" to indicate where to find the photograph. Don't forget to use reference > stated in. You may have to create a wikidata item for the photographer.

Wikidata WikiProject HolyWells

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Saint Augustine's Well (Q122189562)

holy well on Abbey Meadows in Callan, Co. Kilkenny edit

[St. Augustine's Well](#) | [St Augustine's Well](#) | [Abbey Well](#) | [The Old Abbey Well](#) | [The Friars' Well](#)

[In more languages](#)

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Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Saint Augustine's Well	holy well on Abbey Meadows in Callan, Co. Kilkenny	St. Augustine's Well St Augustine's Well Abbey Well The Old Abbey Well The Friars' Well
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

instance of	holy well edit
	2 references
	Holy Well Semantic Concept edit
	0 references
	+ add reference
	spring edit
	1 reference
	architectural structure edit
	0 references
	+ add reference
	+ add value

Saint Augustine's Well in Wikidata

Property	Example/ further qualifiers
instance of (P31)	Holy Well Semantic Concept (Q126443332)
instance of (P31)	<p>holy well (Q1371047)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> state of use (P5817) "in use" for holy wells where veneration is still happening or "abandoned", where that is the case state of conservation (P5816): preserved (Q56557591)/ in danger (Q55555088)/ demolished or destroyed (Q56556915) reference URL (P854): 6 Inch First Edition Ordnance Survey map of Ireland (Q126528008) and/ or Historic Environment Viewer (Ireland) (Q120966194) or any of the ones under described by source (P1343), where it is described as a holy well and not merely a "Spring" or "Well"
instance of (P31)	religious site (Q105889895)
instance of (P31)	water source (Q10713454)/ spring (Q124714)/ water well (Q43483)/ pumping station (Q446013)
instance of (P31)	architectural structure (Q811979)
named after (P138)	Brigit of Kildare (Q80979) eye (Q7364)
feast day (P841)	state of use (P5817)
country (P17)	Ireland (Q27)
located in the administrative territorial entity (P131)	County Kilkenny (Q180231) + Balleen (Q60553357)
diocese (P708)	Roman Catholic Diocese of Ossory (Q873607)
coordinate location (P625)	
street address (P6375)	
described by source (P1343)	<p>O'Kelly: The Place-Names of County Kilkenny (Q126374601)</p> <p>Historic Environment Viewer (Ireland) (Q120966194)</p> <p>The Schools' Collection (Q126393245)</p> <p>Canon W. Carrigan: The History and Antiquities of the Diocese of Ossory (Q126454942) with its volumes</p> <p>6 Inch First Edition Ordnance Survey map of Ireland (Q126528008)</p>
image (P18)	
video (P10)	
Commons category (P373)	Category:Toberbride, Callan ↗
YouTube video ID (P1651)	
external data available at URL (P1325)	diverse

P15 was influenced by

P53 has former or current location

P70 documents

L60i is documented by

E22 Human-Made Object

E39 Actor

E53 Place

E31 Document

D9 Data Object

Holy Well (Wikidata) in CIDOC CRM

Use Cases

CIDOC CRM ... in Open Street Map

OpenStreetMap Ireland

```
1  /*
2  This is an example Overpass query.
3  Try it out by pressing the Run button above!
4  You can find more examples with the Load tool.
5  */
6  node
7    [historic=archaeological_site]
8    ({{{bbox}}});
9  out;
```

overpass-turbo.eu/s/1RvC

OSM als Datenspeicher, hier in Irland

Deutsch Fthierrygeo Diskussion Einstellungen Beobachtungsliste Beiträge Abmelden

Seite Diskussion Lesen Bearbeiten Quelltext bearbeiten Versionsgeschichte

Tag:historic=ogham_stone

English русский

Andere Sprachen...

Cache leeren · Hilfe

A stone with an Ogham script on it.

They are most commonly found in Ireland as free standing stones, lying on the ground, recycled in buildings such as churches or as artefacts in museums.

Inhaltsverzeichnis [Verbergen]

- 1 Usage
- 2 Examples
- 3 Tags to use in combination
- 4 External ressourcen

historic = ogham_stone a · d · b

Description

A stone with an Ogham script on it. They are most commonly found in Ireland as free standing stones, lying on the ground, recycled in buildings such as churches or as artefacts in museums.

Group: historic

Used on these elements

Usage [Bearbeiten | Quelltext bearbeiten]

Set a node and add `historic=ogham_stone`. Add `name=*`, preferably using an established name used in research literature.

Examples [Bearbeiten | Quelltext bearbeiten]

Lamoge, Co. Kilkenny

In this Time Team episode [\(Spoiler alert! \)](#) they find an stone that has ogham on it.

- [Arraglen Ogham Stone on Wikipedia](#)
- [Ballycrovane Ogham Stone on Wikipedia](#)
- [Ballanueenev Ogham Stone on Wikipedia](#)

Deutsch Fthierrygeo Diskussion Einstellungen Beobachtungsliste Beiträge Abmelden

Seite Diskussion Lesen Bearbeiten Quelltext bearbeiten Versionsgeschichte

Tag:place_of_worship=holy_well

English

Andere Sprachen...

Cache leeren · Hilfe

A holy well is a mainly natural source of water which is believed to have healing powers or is associated with supernatural events. To distinguish it from springs without these associations, they have been given a name^[1]. For easier access to the water, there can be stone or pipe structures. Votive offerings can be left by devotees.

Inhaltsverzeichnis [Verbergen]

- 1 Usage
- 2 Examples
- 3 Values
- 4 See also
- 5 References

place_of_worship = holy_well a · d · b

Description

A holy well is a mainly natural source of water which is believed to have healing powers or is associated with supernatural events. To distinguish it from springs without these associations, they have been given a name.

Group: religion

Used on these elements

Requires

- `amenity=place_of_worship`
- `natural=spring` OR `man_made=water_well`

Useful combination

Usage [Bearbeiten | Quelltext bearbeiten]

The value `holy_well` is used to identify a well which is considered a holy well by locals. In most cases, it will be a natural source of water in the shape of a `natural=spring` or less often a `natural=water + water=pond`. Contrary to the word "well" being used, in only very few cases it will be a `man_made=water_well`. However, to give easy access to the water for filling bottles or similar, there can be a stone lining or pipes in place. In some cases, a well house will protect the structure. (See examples below.)

There can be churches, church ruins or rag trees/ wishing trees nearby, which can also be mapped.

Examples [Bearbeiten | Quelltext bearbeiten]

tagging via keys ...

overpass-turbo.eu/s/1RvE

overpass-turbo.eu/s/1RvG

OSM items of Ogham Stones & Holy Wells

```
node  
  [historic=ogham_stone]  
  ({{{bbox}}});  
out;
```

Node 5145413640

Tags 9

historic = ogham_stone
inscription = ERC MAQI MAQI-ERCIAS MU DOVINIA
moved = no
name = CIIC 178
project = ogham.link
ref:IE:smr = KE052-059002-
source = survey
wikidata = Q70892682
wikimedia_commons =
File:Coumeenoole_Ogham_Stone_(Dunmore_Head).jpg

Coordinates
52.1102541 / -10.4731829 (lat/lon)

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Ogham Stone at Dunmore Head in OSM


```
way[place_of_worship=holy_well]({{bbox}});  
(.;>);  
out center;  
node[place_of_worship=holy_well]({{bbox}});  
out center;  
relation[place_of_worship=holy_well]({{bbox}});  
out center;
```

Anne-Karoline Distel, CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Saint Augustine's Well in OSM

P1 is identified by

P56 bears feature

P70 documents

L60i is documented by

How to tag
name
inscription=*
inscription:en=*
inscription:pgl-Latn=*
inscription:pgl-Ogam=*
wikipedia=*
wikidata=*
moved=*
moved_to:wikidata=*
moved_from=*
moved_from:wikidata=*
height=*, width=*
description=*
material=*
source=*
source:inscription=*
source:url=*
ref:IE:nm=*
ref:IE:smr=*
project=*
wikimedia_commons=*
url:sketchfab=*

P1 is identified by

P15 was influenced by

P70 documents

Key=value
amenity=place_of_worship
place_of_worship=holy_well
natural=spring/ man_made=water_well
religion=*
denomination=*
name=*
loc_name=*
other language names
covered=*
saint:name=*
subject:wikipedia=*
subject:wikidata=*
patron_day=*
wikipedia=*
wikidata=*
building
description=*
tourism=attraction

E22 Human-Made Object
E19 Physical Object

Ogham Stones & Holy Wells (OSM) in CIDOC CRM

Use Cases

CIDOC CRM ... in Wikibase-Instanzen

Thiery, F., Schenk, F., Baars, S., Tolle, K., & Thiery, P. (2024). Modellierung von Fuzzyness / Wobbliness in Geodaten. Tagungsband FossGIS-konferenz 2024. FOSSGIS-Konferenz 2024 (FOSSGIS2024), Technische Universität Hamburg. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10571858>

Wikibase Data Model of a (Fuzzy Site)

Main Page **Discussion**

Main Page

There is currently no text in this page. You can search for this page title in other pages, search the related logs, or create this page.

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[Privacy policy](#) [About Fuzzy Spatial Locations](#) [Disclaimers](#) [Mobile view](#)

<https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud>

WikiBase-Instanz in der wikibase.cloud

Berlin, Staatliche Museen zu Berlin, 1873 Fox, 18257570
7,78 g, 29 mm, 12 h

Hortfundanalysen (Stefanie Baars)

There is only the information that the **hoard was found on the river Esaro**, without specifying exactly where on the river course. In the literature, there is information that it was **found "in Crotona"**, by which **the city rather than the province** is meant, otherwise it would have been formulated differently. The urban area of the river course ends shortly after the "Strada Statale 106 Jonica". **The most likely location for the find is along the course of the river between the section just before the motorway and the mouth of the river in the sea.** Since the find was made in 1967, the course of the river at that time probably corresponds fairly closely to the course of the river today. However, both the latter and the presumed find section are conjectures.

Find at Esaro River in 1967

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Add links

Item Discussion

Fiume Esaro 1967 (gennaio) (Q67)

Am 'Fiume Esaro'. [edit](#)

▼ In more languages
Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Fiume Esaro 1967 (gennaio)	Am 'Fiume Esaro'.	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Polish	No label defined	No description defined	
French	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

instance of Archaeological Site [edit](#)

▼ 0 references [+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

has reference P. Attianese (1980) [edit](#)

▼ 0 references [+ add reference](#)

E. A. Arslan (2014) [edit](#)

▼ 0 references [+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

related to <http://openstreetmap.org/way/137318585> [edit](#)

related to type <http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#DubiousMatch>

▼ 0 references [+ add reference](#)

<http://wikidata.org/entity/Q6681> [edit](#)

related to type <http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#DubiousMatch>

▼ 0 references [+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

has coordinate

39°5'7.800"N, 17°6'44.280"E

has certainty level Low

certainty description Es gibt lediglich die Information, dass der Hortfund am Fluss Esaro gefunden wurde, ohne genaue Angabe, wo am Flusslauf. In der Literatur gibt es die Information, dass er "in Crotona" gefunden wurde, womit eher die Stadt als die Provinz gemeint sein dürfte, da es ansonsten anders formuliert worden wäre. Der städtische Bereich des Flusslaufes endet kurz hinter der "Strada Statale 106 Jonica". Am wahrscheinlichsten ist der Fundort am Flusslauf zwischen dem Abschnitt kurz vor der Autobahn und der Flussmündung im Meer. Da der Fund 1967 getätigt wurde, entspricht der damalige Flussverlauf vermutlich ziemlich genau dem heutigen. Sowohl Letzteres als auch der mutmaßliche Fundabschnitt sind jedoch Vermutungen.

method used Georeferencing

acting person Stefanie Baars

has source subtype Paper

has source Textual Description

method description set a point based on P. Attianese (1980) and E. A. Arslan (2014) using OSM Way 137318585

▼ 0 references

Fiume Esaro 1967 (gennaio) [Q67]

via <https://chis.nrcan.gc.ca/volcano-volcan/hazard-risque-en.php>

Wikirictor, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Vor etwa 40.000 yr b2k fand die größte Eruption des Campanian Ignimbrite (CI) in den Phlegräischen Feldern statt.

Map of Lower Danube region showing contrast between modelled (Costa et al. 2012) and observed tephra thickness (this study; Veres et al. 2013). *Inset*: Projected extent of >0.1 cm tephra thickness (Costa et al. 2012).

- ★ Urluia (this study)
- ★ Rasova profile
- 50cm New data: thickness (cm)
- Sites identified by Veres et al. (2013)
- Data points used in Costa et al. (2012)
- Tephra contour (cm): CI-173R model, Costa et al. (2012)

Fitzsimmons et al. (2014), p.76

“In this paper we investigate [...] the site of Urluia Quarry on the Dobrogea loess plateau [...], **some 15 km south of the Danube River**. The site immediately overlies the Quaternary-uplifted Cretaceous-Tertiary-age limestone basement rocks (Munteanu et al., 2008), which were the target of earlier quarrying activities.”

Pötter et al. (2021), p.5

“The Urluia (URL) LPS is **located in an abandoned limestone quarry on the limestone plateau of the Dobrogea** (Fitzsimmons et al., 2013; Fitzsimmons and Hambach, 2014; Obreht et al., 2017).”

Findspot Urluia (Rumänien): stillgelegter Kalksteinbruch?

URLUIA (ROMANIA) = ID: 52
CA. 44.0947, 27.9021

Property	Value
certaintyDesc (fsl:certaintyDesc)	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper (rdf:langString) (i66391:en)
certaintyLevel (fsl:certaintyLevel)	medium (fsl:medium) [x]
hasReference (fsl:hasReference)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fitzsimmons et al., 2014, 2013 (xsd:string) Obrecht et al., 2017 (xsd:string) Pötter et al., 2021 (xsd:string)
partOf (fsl:partOf)	CampanianIginimbriteProject (fsl:CampanianIginimbriteProject) [x]
siteType (fsl:siteType)	ArchaeologicalSite (fsl:ArchaeologicalSite) [x]
spatialType (fsl:spatialType)	InhabitedPlace (fsl:InhabitedPlace) [x]
hasGeometry (gsp:hasGeometry)	csite_52_geom (fsl:csite_52_geom)
type (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity (prov:Entity) [x] Place (goleades:Place) [x] Site (fsl:Site) [x]
comment (rdfs:comment)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langString) (i66391:en)
label (rdfs:label)	Urluia (Romania) (rdf:langString) (i66391:en)
closeMatch (skos:closeMatch)	664132 (gns:664132) [x]
prefLabel (skos:prefLabel)	Urluia (Romania) (rdf:langString) (i66391:en)
scopeNote (skos:scopeNote)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langString) (i66391:en)
is member (rdfs:member) of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity Instances Collection (fsl:Entity_collection) Place Instances Collection (fsl:Place_collection) Site Instances Collection (fsl:Site_collection)
is used (prov:used) of	csite_52_activity (fsl:csite_52_activity)

CLC:code	131
CLC:explanation	See http://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Romania_CLC_Import .
CLC:shapeld	6840
CLC:year	2006
landuse	quarry
source	European Environment Agency (EEA), CORINE Land Cover, 2006
source:ro	Agenția Europeană de Mediu, CORINE Land Cover, 2006

<http://www.openstreetmap.org/way/84975654>

http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/csite_52

Findspot Urluia (Rumänien): stillgelegter Kalksteinbruch?

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In other languages [Add links](#)

Item
Discussion

Urluia (Romania) (Q73) ✎ edit

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot ✎ edit

↳ In more languages [Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Urluia (Romania)	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Polish	No label defined	No description defined	
French	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

instance of ✎ edit

Geological Site ✎ edit

↳ 0 references + add reference

+ add value

has reference ✎ edit

Fitzsimmons et al., 2014 ✎ edit

↳ 0 references + add reference

Fitzsimmons et al., 2013 ✎ edit

↳ 0 references + add reference

Obrecht et al., 2017 ✎ edit

↳ 0 references + add reference

Pötter et al., 2021 ✎ edit

↳ 0 references + add reference

+ add value

related to ✎ edit

<http://openstreetmap.org/way/84975654> ✎ edit

↳ 0 references + add reference

<http://sws.geonames.org/664132> ✎ edit

↳ 0 references + add reference

has coordinate ✎ edit

44°5'40.9"N, 27°54'7.6"E

has certainty level ✎ edit

Medium

certainty description

Fitzsimmons et al. (2014), p.76: "In this paper we investigate [...] the site of Urluia Quarry on the Dobrogea loess plateau [...], some 15 km south of the Danube River. The site immediately overlies the Quaternary-uplifted Cretaceous-Tertiary-age limestone basement rocks (Munteanu et al., 2008), which were the target of earlier quarrying activities."; Pötter et al. (2021), p.5: "The Urluia (URL) LPS is located in an abandoned limestone quarry on the limestone plateau of the Dobrogea (Fitzsimmons et al., 2013; Fitzsimmons and Hambach, 2014; Obrecht et al., 2017)."

method used ✎ edit

Georeferencing

acting person ✎ edit

Fiona Schenk

has source subtype ✎ edit

Paper

has source ✎ edit

Textual Description

method description

set a point based on Fitzsimmons et al. (2014), p.76 and Pötter et al. (2021), p.5 using OSM Way 84975654

↳ 0 references + add reference

+ add value

Urluia (Romania) [Q73]

Item **Discussion**

Auel AU3 (Q70)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot ✎ edit

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Auel AU3	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Polish	No label defined	No description defined	
French	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

instance of Geological Site ✎ edit
▼ 0 references + add reference
+ add value

related to https://kulturdb.de/einobjekt.php?id=23391 ✎ edit
related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch
▼ 0 references + add reference
+ add value

has reference Schenk et al. (2024) ✎ edit
▶ 1 reference + add value

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- In other languages
- ✎ Add links

has coordinate	50°16'57.0"N, 6°35'42.4"E
has certainty level	High
certainty description	stated in scientific paper
method used	Georeferencing
acting person	Fiona Schenk
method description	site survey
has source subtype	Paper
has source	Textual Description

via <https://doi.org/10.3390/quat7020017>, Fig. 1

Auel AU3 [Q70]

Fuzzy Spatial Sites (Wikibase) in CIDOC CRM

Use Cases

CIDOC CRM

**... als Referenzmodell in
relationalen Datenbanken**

via <https://www2.leiza.de/navis/>

NAVIS I ⇒ SHIP WRECKS / RECONSTRUCTIONS / MODELS
 NAVIS II ⇒ SHIP DEPICTIONS ON OBJECTS
 NAVIS III ⇒ SHIPS ON ROMAN COINS

NAVISone aus NAVIS, NAVIS II und NAVIS III

NAVISone relationales Datenschema

- **Main Classes**

- no:O**bject** (**E22** Human-Made Object)
- no:F**eature** (**E25** Human-Made Feature)
- no:K**eyword** (**E55** Type / **Concept**)
- no:L**iterature** (**E31** Document)
- no:D**ating** (**E49** Time Appellation, use **E41** Appellation / **TimeAsAConcept**)
- no:I**mage** (**D9** Data Object, via *CRMdig*)

- **Main Properties**

- crm:P**56** (**P56** bears feature) [**O**→**F**]
- crm:P**164** (**P164** is temporally specified by) [**O**→**D**]
- crm:P**67** (**P67** refers to) [**O/F**→**L**]
- crm:P**2** (**P2** has type) [**O/F**→**K**]
- dig:L**60i** (**L60i** is documented by, via *CRMdig*) [**O/F**→**I**]

NAVISone in CIDOC CRM

via <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-024-06343-x>

... metallurgy of the Sejma-Turbino-Phenomenon

RDMBS-Schema als CIDOC CRM Schema

- **Main Classes**

- crm:E22 (**E22** Human-Made Object)
- crm:E26/E25 (**E26** Physical Feature, **E25** Human-Made Feature)
- crm:E16 (**E16** Measurement)
- crm:E29 (**E29** Design or Procedure)
- crm:E27/E53 (**E27** Site, **E53** Place)
- crm:E54 (**E54** Dimension)
- crm:E58 (**E58** Measurement Unit)
- crm:E57 (**E57** Material)
- crm:E99 (**E99** Product Type)

- **Main Properties**

- crm:P2 (**P2** has type) [**E22**→**E55**; **E22**→**E26**; **E22**→**E25**; **E22**→**E29**; **E22**→**E29**; **E22**→**E53**; **E22**→**E57**]
- crm:P56 (**P56** bears feature) [**E22**→**E26**]
- crm:P39 (**P39** measured) [**E16**→**E22**]
- crm:P39 (**P33** used specific technique) [**E16**→**E29**]
- crm:P40 (**P40** observed dimension) [**E16**→**E54**]
- crm:P91 (**P91** has unit) [**E54**→**E58**]
- crm:P56 (**P56** bears feature) [**E22**→**E26**]
- crm:P39 (**P33** used specific technique) [**E16**→**E29**; **E26**→**E27**]
- crm:P46 (**P46** is composed of) [**E22**→**E57**]
- crm:P128 (**P128** carries) [**E22**→**E25**]
- crm:P189 (**P89** falls within) [**E25**→**E53**]

Metallurgy of the Sejma-Turbino-Phenomenon in CIDOC CRM

Use Cases

CIDOC CRM

... in Research Tools

TiGeR

Von der Korrespondenzanalyse zur *Temporal Map*

TiGeR RDF Visualisierung

- **Main Classes**

- lado:TiGeR_Event / lado:DiscoverySite (**E53** Place / **geo:SpatialObject** / **PlaceAsAConcept** and **D10** Software Execution, via *CRMdig*)

- **Main Properties**

- time:intervalAfter (**P183** ends before the start of?) [**E**→**E**]
- time:intervalBefore (**P183i** starts after the end of?) [**E**→**E**]
- lado:tiger_cax/y ~ lado:tiger_cax_norm/hex
(sub property of **L11** had output?, via *CRMdig*) [**E**→*literal*]

Nur eine
hypothetische
CRM-Modellierung!

TiGeR in CIDOC CRM

ALLIGATOR

	HadriansWall	Neckarlimes	NoordzeeKust	Wetteraulimes
Alblimes	fi	fi	fi	fi
DonauLimesPhase1	<	<	<	<
DonauLimesPhase2	fi	fi	fi	fi
Elisabethenstrasse	<	<	<	<
HadriansWall	=	fi	fi	=
Neckarlimes	f	=	fi	f
NoordzeeKust	f	f	=	f
Wetteraulimes	=	fi	fi	=

Von der Korrespondenzanalyse zum *Allen Kalkül*

A L L I G A T O R

Alligator RDF Visualisierung

- **Main Classes**

- lado:Alligator_Event / time:Interval (**E41** Appellation / **TimeAsAConcept** and **D10** Software Execution, via *CRMdig*)

- **Main Properties**

- alligator:cax/y/z ~ alligator:estimatedStart/End ~ alligator:nfsn/nfen (sub property of **L11** had output?, via *CRMdig*) [**E**→*literal*]
- time:intervalAfter (**P183** ends before the start of?) [**E**→**E**]
- time:intervalbefore (**P183i** starts after the end of?) [**E**→**E**]
- plus all other Allen Relations [**E**→**E**]

CRM dig
Model for provenance metadata

Figure 2 Thirteen elementary possible relations between time periods [af-97].

Alligator in CIDOC CRM

Use Cases

CIDOC CRM

... in studentischen Arbeiten

Sophie C. Schmidt, CC BY 4.0

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

“Brandenburg 5.000 v. Chr.” (Diss. Sophie C. Schmidt)

Sophie C. Schmidt, CC BY 4.0

“Brandenburg 5.000 v. Chr.” (Diss. Sophie C. Schmidt)

- **Main Classes**

- lado:**I**nformation**C**arrier (**E22** Human-Made Object)
- lado:**C**ontext (**A2** Stratigraphic Volume Unit, via *CRMarchaeo*)
- lado:**L**ocation (**E27** Site / **E27** Site / **geo:SpatialObject**)
- lado:**P**lace (**E53** Place / **geo:SpatialObject**)

- **Main Properties**

- lado:partOf (**AP21** contains / **AP21i** is contained in, via *CRMarchaeo*) [**IC** → **C**]
- lado:locatedWithin (**P59** has section) [**C** → **L**]
- lado:hasLocation (**P89** falls within) [**L** → **P**]

CRMarchaeo

Excavation Model

“Brandenburg 5.000 v. Chr.” in CIDOC CRM

Zde, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

aus Schenk, F. et al. (2024), via <https://doi.org/10.3390/quat7020017>

Batholith, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons

Xalaros, Attribution, via Wikimedia Commons

Vor 39'940 yr b2k ± 150 yr fand z.B. die Eruption des Campanian Ignimbrite (CI) in den Phlegräischen Feldern statt

Grafiken: Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

CI Fundort-Ontologie (Diss. Fiona Schenk)

Grafiken: Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

CI Fundort-Ontologie (Diss. Fiona Schenk)

Grafiken: Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

CI Fundort-Ontologie (Diss. Fiona Schenk)

- **Main Classes**

- fsl:Site / **prov:Entity** (E53 Place / **geo:SpatialObject** / **PlaceAsAConcept**)
- foaf:Person / **prov:Agent** (E39 Actor)
- fsl:Georeferencing / **prov:Activity** (E7 Activity)

- **Main Properties**

- prov:wasAttributedTo (**P15** was influenced by?) [**E** → **Ag**]
- prov:wasAssociatedWith (**P14** carried out by?) [**Ac** → **Ag**]
- prov:wasGeneratedBy (**P33** used specific technique?) [**E** → **Ac**]

Nur eine
hypothetische
CRM-Modellierung!

Campanian Ignimbrite in CIDOC CRM

oben: Wilsnack, St. Nikolai, Außenansicht von Südwesten, CVMA Deutschland Potsdam/ Berlin-Brandenburgische Akademie der Wissenschaften, Foto: Holger Kuper; rechts: 3D-Modell: 3D-Modell Kirche St. Nikolai Chor, Büro AXEL SEEMANN - Planung in der Denkmalpflege

links: Struktur der geplanten Forschungsinfrastruktur

rechts: Wilsnack, St. Nikolai, Wunderblutschrein, Außenseite, Gregorsmesse, CVMA Deutschland Potsdam/Berlin- Brandenburgische Akademie der Wissenschaften, Foto: Holger Kuper.

unten: Verknüpfung der Forschungsobjekte mit Ressourcen und Metadateien, Anja Gerber 2022

Forschungsobjekte werden im CVMA DRM erstellt

Zuweisung der Ressourcen zu den Forschungsobjekten

Wilsnack Digital (Anja Gerber)

Wilsnack, Kirche St. Nikolai, Blick in den Chor mit Hochaltarretabel, Foto: Berenike Rensinghoff.

Modellierung Wilsnack Digital

Anhang 4b: Relationen der Forschungsobjekte

Klasse 1 (Entity Domain)	Relation	Klasse 2 (Entity Range)	Beispiel		
E53 Place	P89 falls within (contains)	E53 Place	Für Stadteile und Eingemeindungen anwenden.		
E53 Place	P157 is at rest relative to (provides reference space for)	E18 Physical Thing	Wilsnack bietet Referenzraum für St. Nikolai.		
E53 Place	P59i is located on or within	E18 Physical Thing	St. Nikolai befindet sich in Wilsnack.		
E79 Part Addition	P110 augmented (was augmented by)	E22 Physical Human-Made Object	Hängeepitaph wurde hinzugefügt		
E80 Part removal	P112 diminished (was diminished by)	E22 Physical Human-Made Object	xyz wurde entfernt		
E11 Modification	P31 has modified (was modified by)	E18 Physical Thing	Wurde verändert (von)		
E4 Period	P7 took place (witnessed)	E53 Place	Wilsnackfahrt fand in St. Nikolai statt		
E4 Period	P8 took place on or within (witnessed)	E18 Physical Thing	Wilsnackfahrt fand in Wunderblutkapelle statt		
E5 Event	P12 occurred in the presence of (was present at)	E39 Actor	Die Hostienverbrennung fand in der Anwesenheit von Johann Ellefeldt statt.		E77 Persistent Item
E18 Physical Thing	P53 has former or current location (is former or current location of)	E53 Place	St. Nikolai hat als Standort Wilsnack.		
E24 Physical Human-Made Thing	P53 has former or current location (is former or current location of)	E53 Place	Altar hat als Standort Wilsnack.		
E22 Physical Human-Made Object	P53 has former or current location (is former or current location of)	E53 Place	Fenster nVIII hat als Standort Wilsnack		
E18 Physical Thing	P51 has former or current owner (is former or current owner of).	E39 Actor	St. Nikolai hat als Eigentümer Familie von Saldern.		
E22 Physical Human-Made Object	P51 has former or current owner (is former or current owner of).	E39 Actor			
E24 Physical Human-Made Thing	P51 has former or current owner (is former or current owner of).	E39 Actor	Gegenstand xyz hat als Eigentümer ...		
E39 Actor	P74 has current or former residence (is current or former residence of)	E53 Place	Wilsnack ist die frühere oder aktuelle Residenz der Familie von Saldern.		
E92 Spacetime Volume	P10 falls within (contains)	E92 Spacetime Volume			
E92 Spacetime Volume	P160 has temporal projection (is temporal projection of)	E52 Time-span	Das Hostienwunder hat die zeitliche Projektion 1383.		
E92 Spacetime Volume	P161 has spatial projection (is spatial projection of)	E53 Place	Die Wallfahrt hat die räumliche Projektion Wilsnack, St. Nikolai.		
E63 Begin of existence	P12 occurred in the presence of (was present at)	E39 Actor	Hostienwunder erschien in der Anwesenheit des Pfarrers xyz	E5 Event	E77 Persistent Item
E63 Begin of existence	P12 occurred in the presence of (was present at)	E18 Physical Thing		E5 Event	E77 Persistent Item
E63 Begin of existence	P12 occurred in the presence of (was present at)	E24 Physical Human-Made Thing			
E64 End of existence	P93 took out of existence (was taken out of existence by)	E18 Physical Thing		E5 Event	E77 Persistent Item
E64 End of existence	P93 took out of existence (was taken out of existence by)				
E64 End of existence	P93 took out of existence (was taken out of existence by)				
E63 Begin of existence	P11 had participant (participated in)				

● Main Classes

- **E53** Place
- **E18** Physical thing
- **E22** Physical human-made object
- **E24** Physical human-made thing
- **E4** Period
- **E39** Actor
- **E11** Modification
- **E92** Spacetime volume
- **E63** Beginning of existence
- **E64** End of existence

● Main Properties

- P89 falls within (**P**→**P**)
- P157 proves reference space for (**Pl**→**Pt**)
- P59i is located on or within (**Pt**→**Pl**)
- P10 falls within (**Sv**→**Sv**)
- P53 has former or current location (**Pt/Pho/Pht**→**Pl**)
- P51 has former or current owner (**Pt/Pho/Pht**→**A**)
- P12 occurred in the presence of (**B**→**A**)
- P93 took out of existence (**E**→**Pt/Pho/Pht**)
- P93i was taken out of existence (**E**→**A**)

Nur eine prototypische CRM-Modellierung! Das Projekt endete nach der Explorationsphase 12/2022.

Wilsnack Digital in CIDOC CRM

Use Cases

CIDOC CRM

... along the N40 Objects Biography

Manage Shortcuts agerber Devel WissKI

Content Structure Appearance Extend Configuration People Reports Help

nfdi4objects.wisski.data.fau.de Home Find Navigate Create My account Log out

Home > Navigate

Objekt ☆

Displaying 1 - 12 of 12

 Idia-Elfenbeinanhänger, BM_Af1910_5-13_1					
 Eisenstaublunge					

Objektbiografien in NFDI4Objects: Entwicklungsinstanz in WissKI

Edit Pathbuilder: nfdi4objects_objektbiografie ☆

+ Add Path

+ Add Existing Path

Objekt	Group [nfdi4objects:Object]	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Unlimited	<input type="text" value="Edit"/> <input type="text" value="v"/>
Id	nfdi4objects:Object → crm:P48_has_preferred_identifier → nfdi4objects:Identifier	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Text (plain) 1	<input type="text" value="Edit"/> <input type="text" value="v"/>
Entstehung	Group [nfdi4objects:Object → crm:P92i_was_brought_into_existence_by → crm:E63_Beginning_of_Existence]	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Unlimited	<input type="text" value="Edit"/> <input type="text" value="v"/>
Beauftragung	Group [nfdi4objects:Object → crm:P92i_was_brought_into_existence_by → crm:E63_Beginning_of_Existence → crm:P20i_was_purpose_of → nfdi4objects:Commissioning]	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Unlimited	<input type="text" value="Edit"/> <input type="text" value="v"/>
Akteurzuweisung	nfdi4objects:Object → crm:P92i_was_brought_into_existence_by → crm:E63_Beginning_of_Existence → crm:P20i_was_purpose_of → nfdi4objects:Commissioning → crm:P140i_was_attributed_by → nfdi4objects:Actor_Assignment	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Entity reference Unlimited	<input type="text" value="Edit"/> <input type="text" value="v"/>
Ortszuweisung	nfdi4objects:Object → crm:P92i_was_brought_into_existence_by → crm:E63_Beginning_of_Existence → crm:P20i_was_purpose_of → nfdi4objects:Commissioning → crm:P140i_was_attributed_by → nfdi4objects:Place_Assignment	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Entity reference Unlimited	<input type="text" value="Edit"/> <input type="text" value="v"/>
Zeitzuweisung	nfdi4objects:Object → crm:P92i_was_brought_into_existence_by → crm:E63_Beginning_of_Existence → crm:P20i_was_purpose_of → nfdi4objects:Commissioning → crm:P140i_was_attributed_by → nfdi4objects:Time_Assignment	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Entity reference Unlimited	<input type="text" value="Edit"/> <input type="text" value="v"/>
Kommentar	nfdi4objects:Object → crm:P92i_was_brought_into_existence_by → crm:E63_Beginning_of_Existence → crm:P20i_was_purpose_of → nfdi4objects:Commissioning → crm:P129i_is_subject_of → nfdi4objects:Comment	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Text (plain, long) 1	<input type="text" value="Edit"/> <input type="text" value="v"/>
Quellenverweis	nfdi4objects:Object → crm:P92i_was_brought_into_existence_by → crm:E63_Beginning_of_Existence → crm:P20i_was_purpose_of → nfdi4objects:Commissioning → crm:P129i_is_subject_of → nfdi4objects:Source_Content_Section	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Entity reference Unlimited	<input type="text" value="Edit"/> <input type="text" value="v"/>
Kreation	Group [nfdi4objects:Object → crm:P92i_was_brought_into_existence_by → crm:E63_Beginning_of_Existence → crm:P9_consists_of → crm:E65_Creation]	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1	<input type="text" value="Edit"/> <input type="text" value="v"/>
Akteurzuweisung	nfdi4objects:Object → crm:P92i_was_brought_into_existence_by → crm:E63_Beginning_of_Existence → crm:P9_consists_of → crm:E65_Creation → crm:P140i was attributed by → nfdi4objects:Actor Assianment	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Entity reference Unlimited	<input type="text" value="Edit"/> <input type="text" value="v"/>

Objektbiografien in NFDI4Objects: Screenshot WissKI-Pathbuilder

E22 Man-Made Object
E63 Beginning of
Existence
E12 Production
E52 Time Span
E21 Person
E53 Place

Faktische Modellierung von Merkmalen und
Eigenschaften → nicht so ganz FAIR!
Wie können Informationsprovenienz oder
Unsicherheiten strukturiert abgebildet werden?

Objektbiografien in NFDI4Objects: Modellierungsprinzipien

from <https://www.w3.org/TR/annotation-model/>

Keep in mind!
subjektive Annotationen!

nach "NFDI4Objects Core Ontology und Objektbiografien",
S. Wagner, A. Gerber, CC BY 4.0, via DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10591897.

E22 Man-Made Object
E63 Beginning of
Existence
E12 Production
E13 Attribute
Assignment

Merkmale und Eigenschaften werden über sog. **Zuweisungsereignisse** (Annotationen) modelliert. Ereignisse erlauben es, Informationen besser zu kontextualisieren.

Objektbiografien in NFDI4Objects: Modellierungsprinzipien

Entstehung	
Herstellung	
Akteurzuweisung	
Person	Leygebe, Gottfried
Quellenverweis	
Wortlaut	"[...] von Gottfried Leygeber [...] verfertigt [...]"
Quelle	Inventar der Berliner Kunstammer von 1694, S. 232

Um Annotationen für Dritte nachvollziehbar zu machen und die Informationsprovenienz zu heben → Zuweisung von Quellen

Objektbiografien in NFDI4Objects: Modellierungsprinzipien

siehe auch... Modellierungen in Wikibase-Instanzen

- **Main Classes (Auswahl)**

- nfdi4objects:Object (E22)
- crm:E63_Beginning_of_Existence
- nfdi4objects:Actor_Assignment (E13 Attribute Assignment)
- nfdi4objects:Place_Assignment (E13 Attribute Assignment)
- nfdi4objects:Time_Assignment (E13 Attribute Assignment)
- crm:E7_Activity (z. B. Grabung, Objektdokumentation)
- crm:E12_Production *als Beispiel für ein Ereignis E5 bzw. eine Aktivität E7*
- crm:E19_Physical_Object
- crm:E20_Biological_Object
- nfdi4objects:Source_Content_Section
- nfdi4objects:Material_Assignment (E17 Type Assignment)
- crm:E21_Person
- crm:E53_Place (z.B. Geographischer Ort, die sich auch in Gazetteers wiederfinden
bspw. Erlangen, Park an der Ilm, Location sehr genaue Orte, die durch Koordinaten angegeben werden, bspw. Fundstellen)

- **Main Properties (Auswahl)**

- crm:P92i_was_brought_into_existence_by (O→B)
- crm:P140i_was_attributed_by (P→AA/PA/TA) → *E12 steht hier als Bsp. für die Zuweisung von Akteuren/Orten/Zeit z. E. bestimmten Ereignis*
- crm:P9_consists_of (O/B→P)
- crm:P129i_is_subject_of (O/B→P→SCS)
- crm:P16_used_specific_object (P→PO/BO)
- crm:P12i_was_present_at (Pe→A/P)
- crm:P11_had_participant (A/P→Pe)
- crm:P53_has_former_or_current_location (O/PO/BO→Pl)

Befindet sich in der Entwicklung,
Use Cases gesucht.
Dokumentation der Entwicklungen:
<https://github.com/nfdi4objects/n4o-ontology>

Objektbiografien in NFDI4Objects in CIDOC CRM

Conclusio & Up Next ...

Community Cluster:
Semantic Modelling & LOD

Arbeitsgruppe:
Objekt-Ontologie / MMDS

NFDI lebt von der aktiven Mitarbeit

Arbeitsgruppe:
Objekt-Ontologie / MMDS

TWG N40 OO und MMDS

Hin zum NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph

NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph

 NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph | SPARQL | Cypher | **Collections** | Repositories | Terminologies | Manual

A collection is an individual set of research data imported into the knowledge graph. Each collection is identified by a URI starting with <https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/>. Each collection belongs to a [research data repository](#) where its data has been published.

Information about collections is stored in the RDF graph <https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/>.

collection	name	repository	license
1 n4oc:1	Ur- und Frühgeschichtliche Sammlung der FAU	wd:Q124695065	
2 n4oc:2	Paläontologischen Sammlung der FAU Geowissenschaftliche Sammlung der FAU	wd:Q124695065	
3 n4oc:3	Graphische Sammlung der FAU	wd:Q124695065	
4 n4oc:4	Musikinstrumentensammlung der FAU	wd:Q124695065	
5 n4oc:5	Medizinische Sammlung der FAU	wd:Q124695065	
6 n4oc:6	Schulgeschichtliche Sammlung der FAU und Schulmuseum	wd:Q124695065	
7 n4oc:7	KENOM Virtuelles Münzportal (via LIDO)	wd:Q21040628	
8 n4oc:8	Samian Research Database	wd:Q22661177	https://www.hbz-nrw.de/produkte/open-access/lizenzen/dppl/mdppl/m-DPPL_v3_en_11-2008
9 n4oc:9	Linked Open Ogham	wd:Q22661177	http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
10 n4oc:10	African Red Slip Ware	wd:Q22661177	http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
11 n4oc:11	Digitale Sammlungen der Museen der Klassikstiftung Weimar	wd:Q124536091	
12 n4oc:12	Graphische Sammlung des Germanisches National Museum	wd:Q478695	
13 n4oc:13	KENOM (via Nomisma)	wd:Q24578999	

N4O Knowledge Graph

<https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/sparql>

Samian Research Database

<https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/8>

Loaded into the graph at 2024-09-24T09:11:00+00:00 with 7764422 triples.

Homepage: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13832255>

Quell-Repository: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q22661177>

Lizenz der Daten: https://www.hbz-nrw.de/produkte/open-access/lizenzen/dppl/mdppl/m-DPPL_v3_en_11-2008

Please use SPARQL to get more information about the collection such as used classes and used properties.

7764'422

```

@prefix dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#> .
@prefix dcterm: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/> .
@prefix foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/> .
@prefix j: <http://schema.org/> .
@prefix j:4: <http://purl.org/spar/fabio/> .
@prefix skos: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .

<https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/8> a j:4:Database,
    dcat:Dataset ;
    dcterm:isPartOf <https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/> ;
    dcterm:issued "2024-09-24T09:11:00+00:00"^^xsd:dateTime ;
    dcterm:license "https://www.hbz-nrw.de/produkte/open-access/lizenzen/dppl/mdppl/m-DPPL_v3_en_11-2008" ;
    j:2:name "Samian Research Database" ;
    skos:notation "8" ;
    foaf:homepage <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13832255> .
    
```

African Red Slip Ware

<https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/10>

Loaded into the graph at 2024-09-06T08:26:00+00:00 with 64531 triples.

Homepage: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5642751>

Quell-Repository: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q22661177>

Lizenz der Daten: <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Please use SPARQL to get more information about the collection such as used classes and used properties.

64'531

```

@prefix dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#> .
@prefix dcterm: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/> .
@prefix foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/> .
@prefix j:2: <http://schema.org/> .
@prefix j:4: <http://purl.org/spar/fabio/> .
@prefix skos: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .

<https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/10> a j:4:Database,
    dcat:Dataset ;
    dcterm:isPartOf <https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/> ;
    dcterm:issued "2024-09-06T08:26:00+00:00"^^xsd:dateTime,
        "2024-09-06T07:00:00+00:00"^^xsd:dateTime,
        "2024-09-06T08:26:00+00:00"^^xsd:dateTime ;
    dcterm:license "http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/" ;
    j:2:name "African Red Slip Ware" ;
    skos:notation "10" ;
    foaf:homepage <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5642751> .
    
```

Linked Open Ogham

<https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/9>

Loaded into the graph at 2024-09-06T08:26:00+00:00 with 102114 triples.

Homepage: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4765603>

Quell-Repository: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q22661177>

Lizenz der Daten: <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Please use SPARQL to get more information about the collection such as used classes and used properties.

102'114

```

@prefix dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#> .
@prefix dcterm: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/> .
@prefix foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/> .
@prefix j:2: <http://schema.org/> .
@prefix j:4: <http://purl.org/spar/fabio/> .
@prefix skos: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .

<https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/9> a j:4:Database,
    dcat:Dataset ;
    dcterm:isPartOf <https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/> ;
    dcterm:issued "2024-09-06T08:26:00+00:00"^^xsd:dateTime,
        "2024-09-06T07:00:00+00:00"^^xsd:dateTime,
        "2024-09-06T08:26:00+00:00"^^xsd:dateTime ;
    dcterm:license "http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/" ;
    j:2:name "Linked Open Ogham" ;
    skos:notation "9" ;
    foaf:homepage <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4765603> .
    
```

NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph

SPARQL endpoint `/api/sparql` (see [documentation](#))

```

1 PREFIX geosparql: <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>
2 PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
3 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
4 PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
5 SELECT ?item ?label ?geo WHERE {
6   ?item a oghamonto:OghamSite.
7   ?item rdfs:label ?label.
8   ?item geosparql:hasGeometry ?item_geom.
9   ?item_geom geosparql:asWKT ?geo.
10 }
    
```

Annascaul (Ogham Site)
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000003>

The Annascaul (Ogham Site) resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unions OGS Plugin

Search: Download options: normal | Turtle | TTL | Download

Property	Value
exactMatch (oghamonto:exactMatch)	OS40000003 (rdf:type oghamonto:OghamSite)
label_bare (oghamonto:label_bare)	Annascaul (rdf:type)
label_country (oghamonto:label_country)	Ireland (rdf:type)
label_county (oghamonto:label_county)	Kerry (rdf:type)
label_province (oghamonto:label_province)	Munster (rdf:type)
label_switzerland (oghamonto:label_switzerland)	Annascaul (rdf:type)
oghamonto:oghamonto (oghamonto:oghamonto:oghamonto)	OS40000003 (rdf:type oghamonto:OghamSite)
hasGeometry (pp:hasGeometry)	OS40000003_geom (rdf:type oghamonto:OghamSite)
type (rdf:type)	oghamonto:OghamSite (rdf:type)
label (rdf:label)	Annascaul (Ogham Site) (rdf:type)
is_member (rdf:member) of	Annascaul (Ogham Site) (rdf:type)

Property	Value
creator (terms:creator)	0000-0000-2000-0000 (0000-0000-2000-0000) (rdf:type)
license (terms:license)	deed de (deed.de) (rdf:type)
oghamonto:oghamonto (oghamonto:oghamonto:oghamonto)	OS40000003 (rdf:type oghamonto:OghamSite)
isData (void:isData)	linked_ogham_ogham (rdf:type linked_ogham_ogham) (rdf:type)
oghamonto:oghamonto (oghamonto:oghamonto:oghamonto)	oghamonto:oghamonto (rdf:type oghamonto:OghamSite)
oghamonto:oghamonto (oghamonto:oghamonto:oghamonto)	oghamonto:oghamonto (rdf:type oghamonto:OghamSite)
oghamonto:oghamonto (oghamonto:oghamonto:oghamonto)	oghamonto:oghamonto (rdf:type oghamonto:OghamSite)

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Table Response 231 results

item	label
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000001>	"Bennettsbridge (Ogham Site)"@en
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000002>	"Drumlohan (Ogham Site)"@en
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000003>	"Aghacarrible (Ogham Site)"@en
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000004>	"Aghaleague (Ogham Site)"@en
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000005>	"Aghascreabagh (Ogham Site)"@en
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000006>	"Aglisk (Ogham Site)"@en
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000007>	"Ahalisky (Ogham Site)"@en
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000008>	"Annagap (Ogham Site)"@en
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000009>	"Annascaul (Ogham Site)"@en
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000010>	"Ardcanaght (Ogham Site)"@en
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000011>	"Ardref (Ogham Site)"@en
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000012>	"Ardocheasty (Ogham Site)"@en
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000013>	"Ardrinane (Ogham Site)"@en
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000014>	"Ardwanig (Ogham Site)"@en
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000015>	"Arraglen (Ogham Site)"@en
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000016>	"Aultagh (Ogham Site)"@en
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000017>	"Ballineesteenig (Ogham Site)"@en
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000018>	"Ballinarry (Ogham Site)"@en
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000019>	"Ballinrannig (Ogham Site)"@en
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000020>	"Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)"@en

Simple view Ellipse Filter query results

geo
"nan"^^geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-7.468056 52.163056)"^^geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-10.176111 52.129444)"^^geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-9.330833 54.260278)"^^geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-7.047778 54.699444)"^^geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-10.138056 52.133056)"^^geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-8.846944 51.678889)"^^geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-10.063056 52.159167)"^^geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-10.061076 52.152143)"^^geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-9.773611 52.165556)"^^geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-9.772778 52.328889)"^^geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-7.729167 51.944167)"^^geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-10.049167 52.143056)"^^geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-9.662778 52.147778)"^^geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-10.236944 52.2675)"^^geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-9.088056 51.770833)"^^geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-10.2075 52.140556)"^^geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-8.377222 52.381944)"^^geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-10.386111 52.176111)"^^geo:wktLiteral
"POINT(-10.031111 52.1725)"^^geo:wktLiteral

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N4O Knowledge Graph | <https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/sparql>

NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph SPARQL | Cypher

SPARQL endpoint `/api/sparql` (see documentation)

```

1 PREFIX geosparql: <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>
2 PREFIX lado: <http://archaeology.link/ontology#>
3 PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
4 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
5 SELECT ?item ?label ?geo (count(?item) AS ?count) WHERE {
6   ?ic lado:hasKilnsite <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_pc_2000042> .
7   ?ic lado:disclosedAt ?item .
8   ?item geosparql:hasGeometry ?geom_obj .
9   ?geom_obj geosparql:asWKT ?geo .
10  OPTIONAL {?item rdfs:label ?label}
11 } GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ORDER BY DESC(?count)
    
```


N4O Knowledge Graph

<https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/sparql>

item	label	geo	count
1 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1001015>	"Reims"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(4.033333 49.25)"@geo:wktLiteral	"22"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
2 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1001549>	"Les Allieux"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(5.090895 49.192956)"@geo:wktLiteral	"12"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
3 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1002190>	"Valkenburg"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(4.433332 52.18333)"@geo:wktLiteral	"8"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
4 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1001633>	"Vechten"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(5.168262 52.060794)"@geo:wktLiteral	"17"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
5 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1001255>	"Tongeren"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(5.46484 50.78054)"@geo:wktLiteral	"17"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
6 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1001351>	"Voorburg"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(4.349213 52.060064)"@geo:wktLiteral	"15"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
7 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1002376>	"Trier"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(6.633333 49.75)"@geo:wktLiteral	"15"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
8 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1000902>	"Niederbieber"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(7.471947 50.467026)"@geo:wktLiteral	"15"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
9 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1000302>	"Rouen"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(1.083333 49.43333)"@geo:wktLiteral	"14"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
10 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1000561>	"Bavay"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(3.7937199999999995 50.29828)"@geo:wktLiteral	"14"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
11 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1003939>	"Zugmantel"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(8.203443 50.189704)"@geo:wktLiteral	"14"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
12 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1004150>	"Forêt de Complègne"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(2.883333 49.366664)"@geo:wktLiteral	"13"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
13 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1002021>	"Zwammerdam"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(5.2099998)"@geo:wktLiteral	"13"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
14 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1003111>	"Heerlen"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(5.983333 50.900001)"@geo:wktLiteral	"13"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
15 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1000136>	"London"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(-0.09184 51.51279)"@geo:wktLiteral	"12"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
16 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1000062>	"York"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(-1.083333 53.96667)"@geo:wktLiteral	"12"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
17 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1000080>	"Colchester"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(0.899999 51.883338)"@geo:wktLiteral	"12"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
18 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1001626>	"Le Pont-des-Rèmes"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(4.949999 49.1333)"@geo:wktLiteral	"12"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
19 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1000137>	"Dalheim"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(6.259722 49.540828)"@geo:wktLiteral	"12"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
20 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1000045>	"Xanten"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(6.45297 51.65877)"@geo:wktLiteral	"12"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
21 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1003244>	"Enfield"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(-0.06 51.643177)"@geo:wktLiteral	"11"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>
22 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1000375>	"Lincoln"@en	"<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(-0.533333 53.233333)"@geo:wktLiteral	"11"@@<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer>

NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph

SPARQL

SPARQL endpoint [/api/sparql](https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/sparql) (see [documentation](#))

TOTAL 18 ARS OBJECTS LOAD!

Sort attributes
 label inventory number

Result style attributes
 boxes list

Active filter

object shape
bowl

object condition
complete

Filter labels & identifiers

Q enter search string

Filter keywords

- Object Type
- Object Shape
- Object Material
- Object Condition
- Object Manufacturing Type
- Object Findspot
- Object Residence
- Object Period
- Object Group
- Object Statement
- Getty AAT
- Wikidata
- Feature Type
- Feature Manufacturing Type
- Feature Statement
- Feature Observation Item Class
- Feature Observation Item


```

1 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
2 PREFIX crm: <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/>
3 PREFIX ars: <http://ars3D/documentation/ontology/arsonto#>
4
5 SELECT DISTINCT ?obj ?label ?identifier WHERE {
6   ?obj rdfs:label ?label.
7   ?obj crm:P1_is_identified_by ?id42.
8   ?id42 rdfs:label ?identifier.
9   ?obj ars:hasShape ars:acd64083-d3ab-4e1d-91d8-f2b043000001.
10  ?obj crm:P44_has_condition ars:4b97fd03-3423-48e1-a61c-c02f21000001.
11 } ORDER BY ASC(?label)

```

obj	label	identifier
<http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/95c8cc98-06a8-4bb6-a85b-fcc93c98689f>	'bowl with Abraham and Isaac'@en	'0.40573'@en
<http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/4dc14582-fb7f-4d5e-a14d-79271ee733a3>	'bowl with Adam and Eve'@en	'0.39768'@en
<http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/2c81898a-647b-4527-a3ba-544e918460ca>	'bowl with Hercules and Minerva'@en	'0.40576'@en
<http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/595257bc-f279-49d0-bd69-9fbca4d63dab>	'bowl with Hercules and the apples of the Hesperides'@en	'0.39780'@en
<http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/8dd07582-bdda-4e94-b4dc-e944b160cf51>	'bowl with Lazarus'@en	'0.40868'@en
<http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/9bbd03c5-33a3-4682-90f1-4ddd6c7fe57d>	'bowl with Minerva'@en	'0.40866'@en
<http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/47def21b-ca45-4dbd-9eac-899956149b1d>	'bowl with animal hunt'@en	'0.40761'@en
<http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/6b46eb63-a258-4076-963f-49b2d0a8530f>	'bowl with boat and baskets'@en	'0.40719'@en
<http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/10e6f99f-172d-47ba-aa3b-4ff348de888c>	'bowl with erots and grapes'@en	'0.41944'@en
<http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/09114937-85ef-4bf5-bca0-351696030cd2>	'bowl with fishes'@en	'0.39846'@en
<http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/e4becf0-90de-4c14-b40a-34c1962c04bc>	'bowl with foxes and trees'@en	'0.41945'@en
<http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/6b5c47ad-82d9-4e20-a2f1-57b357a1df22>	'bowl with hare and baskets'@en	'0.40742'@en
<http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/a8437964-4402-4c7e-ba58-2b80b585e8c0>	'bowl with lions and Kantharos'@en	'0.40574'@en
<http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/1a212bd2-666e-41f3-871f-0a33de751576>	'bowl with martyr and bear'@en	'0.41911'@en
<http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/29282a82-c498-4ec7-ab07-94846a9f84ac>	'bowl with men and lion'@en	'0.41752'@en
<http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/9385f9d6-2523-4c71-a520-07544a35b8f5>	'bowl with palmetto'@en	'0.40747'@en
<http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/554ce8ce-fa32-4cb1-8466-31500e9ab32>	'bowl with quadriga and bear'@en	'0.39896'@en
<http://java-dev.rqzgm.de/ars/objects/64c2cb47-bbfc-44c4-9108-3dd6859150f0>	'bowl with sitting human, lion and leopard'@en	'0.39895'@en

Showing 1 to 18 of 18 entries

N4O Knowledge Graph

<https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/sparql>

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Einfaches CIDOC CRM-Modell

data qualification with metadata for research collections

We have to model **metadata** for the assignments!

via <https://github.com/Research-Squirrel-Engineers/n4o-oo-mmds/blob/main/owl/n4o-oo.owl>

The screenshot displays a web-based ontology editor interface. The left pane shows a class hierarchy for 'Human-Made Feature', which is a subclass of 'Physical Human-Made Thing', 'Feature', and 'Human-Made Object'. The right pane shows the 'Annotations' for 'Human-Made Feature', listing labels in various languages: English (Human-Made Feature), German (Hergestelltes Merkmal), Russian (Искусственный Признак), French (Caractéristique fabriquée), Portuguese (Característica Fabricada), and Chinese (Human-Made Feature). Below the annotations, the 'Description' section shows that 'Human-Made Feature' is equivalent to 'Physical Human-Made Thing'.

Beispiel-Ontologie für die N4O-OO based on LADO

Finis!
Danke :-)

Questions?

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